

SUNFLOWER HYBRIDS IN THE CLIMATIC CONDITIONS OF THE YEAR 2020 IN CONSTANTA COUNTY - SOUTH EAST OF DOBROGEA, ROMANIA

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Abstract. *The experimental field was placed in Amzacea, Constanta County at S.C. SPORT AGRA S.R.L., Center of Development, on the highway 38, 20 km. far from Bulgarian border. Constanta County had the largest weight regarding the surface cultivated in Romania with sunflower crop between 10-12%. The most drought area in Romania is Dobrogea (average 1961-1990: 464 mm. rainfall). Climatic change in recent years has accentuated this tendency. The number of hybrids taken into account in our experiment were twenty. Genesis has been planted in two periods of the time. When the planting was delayed the yield was decreased 303 kg/ha. The aim of this study was i) the behaviour of the hybrids in the unbelievable dry conditions, ii) to see the yield and the behaviour of sunflower hybrids to the attack of main pathogens - *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Phomopsis helianthi*, *Orobanche cumana*, iii) how the planting date influence de yield, iii) the importance of the pesticides used.*

Keywords: sunflower, technological improvement, pest behaviour, yield, drought

1. Introduction

Constanta County (Dobrogea area), had the largest weight regarding the surface cultivated in Romania with sunflower crop (11.10%) from arable land in 2020, and 20.63% from Constanta area arable land (General Direction of Agriculture and Development, Constanta, 2020) [4].

Nowadays there is a wide offer for sunflower hybrids which means without a screening of them is hard to decide which are the most suitable for every region. It should exist experimental fields not only for sunflower but for other important crops related to a specific region. The hybrids must be from different seed companies eliminating any suspicions. In Dobrogea such experiments were made over the years (Jinga et al., 2016; Manole et al., 2018a, 2018b, 2019) [5, 7, 8, 9] which provided results for yield in very dry conditions, behavior to the attack of the main pathogens and quality indices. Here is the first paragraph. The line spacing options are: single, 0 before the paragraph and 6 points after.

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The purposes of this study were: (i) to study the behaviour of the hybrids in the unbelievable dry conditions, (ii) to evaluate the yield and the behaviour of sunflower hybrids to the attack of main pathogens – *Orobanche cumana*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Phomopsis helianthi*, *Alternaria helianthi*, (iii) to assess how the planting date influence de yield, and (iv) to appreciate the importance of the pesticides use.

2. Materials and Methods

The experimental plots were organized in 2020 in the field of SC SPORT AGRA SRL Amzacea, Constanta County (South-East of Romania) (Figure 1). The number of hybrids taken into account have been twenty. The soil is a cambic chernoziom with a deeper profile than other chernozioms, a blackish-brown soil of 40-50 cm thickness, medium texture (Demeter, 2009) [2].

The content of nutrients was: mobile P index -72; N index -4; K index -200; humus -3.11%; neutral pH -7.2. The area of each plot was 672 m². The preceding crop was winter wheat. Planting date was March 12th. Depth of planting 7-8 cm. in considerations of moisture of the soil.

Fig. 1. Experimental field of SC SPORT AGRA SRL Amzacea, Constanta County, 2020 (Original)

The seeds have been treated against (i) *Botrytis* and *Sclerotinia* phytopathogens using Maxim 025 FS (fludioxonil 25g/l) at 0.6 l/100 kg, (ii) *Plasmopara helianthi* using Apron XL (metalaxil 339 g/l) at 3 l/t. In order to protect the seeds were'nt been treated before planting with neonicotinoids (iii) *Tanymecus dilaticollis* Gyll.. Right here it's a most infested area for Romania point of you. We have used after emergence of the crop insecticides two times in order to protect the crop.

Two fungicides were used in vegetative season, to control the pathogens: Mirage 45EC (procloraz 45%) - 1 l/ha 8-10 leaves, and Pictor (200g/l dimoxistrobin + 200g/l boscalid) - 0.5 l/ha before flowering.

To control weeds, the herbicides used were: glyphosate, autumn application, in a dose of 2 l/ha, Frontier Forte (dimetenamid-P) in a dose of 1.4 l/ha, Racer 25EC

(fluorocloridon) in a dose of 2 l/ha, mixed up before emergence and Pulsar Plus (25g/l imazamox) in a dose of 2 l/ha (used only for the imazamox resistant hybrids), at 6-8 leaves. Sulfonylurea was been applied for the hybrids resistant to the herbicides tribenurom methyl 30g./ha.

The soil was fertilized using complex fertilizers (18.46.0 + 20 SO₃) 200 kg/ha and nitrogen in vegetation two trips using 150kg/ha plus 100 kg/ha.

Foliar fertilizers were performed using two complex fertilizers: 12.60.0 - 2 kg/ha and 145 SO₃, 5 MgO, 100 B, 2 Cu, 25 Fe, 50 Mn, 0.5 Mo, 20 Zn - 2 kg/ha.

Fig. 2. Sowing (Original)

Fig. 3. Temperature of the soil in the moment of sowing (Original)

Fig. 4. Experimental field, 5-6 leaves (Original)

Phytopathological assessments of plants were performed on July 17th over the main pathogens: *Phomopsis helianthi* Munt.-Cvet. et al., *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Lib.) de Bary, *Alternaria helianthi* (Hansf.) Tubaki & Nishihara and the parasite *Orobanche cumana* Wallr.. The degree of attack (DA%) was calculated using formula $F \times I/100$ (F - frequency of the attacked plants I - intensity of plants attack).

Fig. 5. *Orobanche cumana*, Onestar (Original)

Technological sheet includes data about number of plants/m² after emergence, flowering and harvesting date and the yield at 9% moisture kg/ha.

Rainfall during 2020 in Amzacea, reveal that, 2020 was the driest year at the time has been with 133 mm. rainfall during the growing season compared with 2019 when the rainfall sum was 178.5 mm (Table 1).

Table 1. Rainfall during 2019 and 2020 growing season of sunflower (Amzacea, Constanta)

	Month								Sum
	Jan.	Feb.	March	Apr	May	June	July	Aug.	
Days	The growing season 2019: Rainfall (mm) for 10-day periods								Sum
1-10	10	0	10	19	0	10	12	7	68
11-20	26	8	0	1	6	4	22	0	67
21-31	0	0	6	15.5	12	0	10	0	43,5
Sum	36	8	16	35.5	18	14	44	7	178,5
Days	The growing season 2020: Rainfall (mm) for 10-day periods								Sum
1-10	0	20	0	0	18	4	29	2	73
11-20	0	0	0	4	0	10	0	0	14
21-31	2	8	16	6	14	0	0	0	46
Sum	2	28	16	10	32	14	29	2	133
Days	Average 1961-1990: monthly values of rainfall (mm)								Sum
1-31	27.7	24.0	29.1	31.8	37.7	47.1	38.9	37.4	464.0

Fig. 6. The height of the hybrids (Original)

Fig. 7. The height of the hybrids (Original)

3. Results and Discussions

The very dry conditions of the year 2020 has affected the height of the hybrids between 70 cm. (FD15E27, Genesis) to 105 cm.(P64LE25, P64LE99).

The diseases can affect the yield and hybrids presented a DA greater or less due to their resistance linked with the climatic conditions.

In 2020, the attack of *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* all of twenty hybrids were'nt been affected. *Phomopsis helianthi* and *Orobanche cumana* had a lower DA average. ES Genesis CL 2 and SY NX82214 (Onestar) CLP had a great DA average for pathogens and parasite combined (8,12% - 7%) (Table 2).

Table 2. Phytosanitary status (DA%) – July 17 2020

Hybrid	Pathogen			Parasite
	<i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i>	<i>Phomopsis helianthi</i>	<i>Alternaria helianthi</i>	<i>Orobanche cumana</i>
<i>ES Genesis CL</i>	0	8	10	1
<i>ES Genesis CL 2</i>	0	10	20	2.5
<i>ES Janis CL</i>	0	5	12	0
<i>ES Anthemis CLP</i>	0	10	8	0
<i>ES Terramis CL</i>	0	12	15	0
<i>Loris CLP</i>	0	8	10	0
<i>Coloris CL</i>	0	10	6	0
<i>SY Odessa CLP</i>	0	8	0	0
<i>SY Diamantis CL</i>	0	11	0	0
<i>SY NX82212 (Nexus) CLP</i>	0	12	8	0
<i>SY NX82214 (Onestar) CLP</i>	0	20	8	2
<i>RGT Absolute CL</i>	0	12	14	0
<i>RGT Eiffell CL</i>	0	16	10	0
<i>FD15CL44</i>	0	10	8	2.5
<i>ES Aromatic SU</i>	0	0	2	3
<i>SY NX81220 SU</i>	0	15.5	12	0
<i>P65LE99</i>	0	6	10	0
<i>P64LE25</i>	0	2	8	0
<i>P64LE137</i>	0	8	10.5	0
<i>FD15E27</i>	0	10	7	0
<i>FD18E41</i>	0	8	12	0.2

All the hybrids tested had over 6 plants/ m² after emergence which means a good an uniform emergence. The average yield of the tested hybrids exceeded the County average yield, because majority of the area cultivated with sunflower have been destroyed of the unbelievable dry conditions with an average yield around 900-1,000 kg/ha (General Direction of Agriculture and Development, Constanta) [4].

The best hybrid from those twenty hybrids wich have been tested in the experimental field was FD15E27 with 1,914 kg/ha, belongs to National Agricultural Research and Development Institute Fundulea, Romania, followed by P64LE25 with 1,779 kg/ha.

Except Genesis 2 all the hybrids had over 6 plants/ m² after emergence. Flowering date was different due their genetic hybrids. Considering the hybrids, all of them had a yield lower than the other years because this year was unforgettable looking to the very dry conditions.

In 2020, when Genesis was planted with a delay of 22 days the yield has decreased with almost 303 kg/ha (Table 3). Same results were recorded in literature showed a higher duration for seed maturity increases yield in sunflower crop (Jonhson and Jellum, 1972; Ahmed et al., 2015; Demir, 2019) [6, 1, 3].

Table 3. Technological sheet for sunflower - 2020

Hybrid	No. of plants/m ² after emergence	Flowering date	Harvesting date	Yield at 9% moisture (kg/ha)
<i>ES Genesis CL</i>	6.5	June 21	August 11	1,593
<i>ES Genesis CL 2</i>	5.5	July 8	August 18	1,290
<i>ES Janis CL</i>	6.5	June 25	August 11	1,428
<i>ES Anthemis CLP</i>	6.5	June 25	August 11	1,774
<i>ES Terramis CL</i>	6.5	June 28	August 11	1,555
<i>Loris CLP</i>	6.5	June 29	August 18	1,420
<i>Coloris CL</i>	6.5	July 2	August 18	1,514
<i>SY Odessa CLP</i>	6	June 25	August 18	1,357
<i>SY Diamantis CL</i>	6.5	June 27	August 18	1,415
<i>SY NX82212 (Nexus) CLP</i>	6.5	June 25	August 11	1,345
<i>SY NX82214 (Onestar) CLP</i>	6	June 25	August 11	1,227
<i>RGT Absolute CL</i>	6.5	July 2	August 11	1,565

<i>RGT Eiffell CL</i>	6.5	July 2	August 18	1,341
<i>FD15CL44</i>	6.5	June 29	August 18	1,343
<i>ES Aromatic SU</i>	6.5	June 26	August 11	1,617
<i>SYNX81220 SU</i>	6.5	June 20	August 11	1,432
<i>P65LE99</i>	6.5	June 29	August 18	1,537
<i>P64LE25</i>	6.5	June 29	August 18	1,779
<i>P64LE137</i>	6.5	June 29	August 11	1,745
<i>FD15E27</i>	6.5	July 2	August 18	1,914
<i>FD18E41</i>	6.5	July 2	August 18	1,375

Fig. 8. Harvesting day 2020 (Original)

Fig. 9. Harvesting day 2020 (Original)

Conclusions

(1) *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* no any chance for attack and *Alternaria helianthi* had a lower attack, also *Phomopsis helianthi*, *Orobanche cumana* had a lower attack. The hybrids planted in March 12th had a lower attack of pathogens: ES Genesis March *Orobanche cumana* DA 1%, *Alternaria helianthi* DA 10%, *Phomopsis helianthi* DA 8% , ES Genesis April *Orobanche cumana* DA 2,5%, *Alternaria helianthi* DA 20%, *Phomopsis helianthi* DA 10%.

(2) When the planting was delayed the yield was decreased with 303 kg/ha(ES Genesis planted in April 4th yielded up 1,290 kg/ha and ES Genesis planted in March 12th 1,593 kg/ha).

(3) Taking into consideration the special climatic conditions, for plants cultivation, in Dobrogea area – South-Eastern Romania, it must be established the best cultivars, adapted to this situation.

(4) Testing sunflower hybrids which already are commercialized in the seed market, or some new hybrids, it could be recomanded the best ones, suitable for this area.

(5) The results in 2020 were very different regarding the climatic conditions, the cultivated plants being high influenced about dryness.

(6) All important pathogens had not conditions for developing in 2020, so, their attack was significantly lower in this year. The same situation was for de attack of the parasite *Orobanche cumana*.

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ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN AREA BETWEEN 2014-2018: A STATISTICAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *European mountains protection represents one of the most important holdings of the European desideratum. As known, mountains offer higher quality in all living, namely biodiversity of air – water – soil. The ecosystem of mountain area is designed to sustain a better life for human being and its adjacent environment. Mountain area is important because the ecosystem and the determinants of this area affect its food system. High altitude areas (mountains) are less polluted than low altitude areas (plains). The paper synthesized data regarding relevant indices, especially regarding business demography statistics and high growth enterprise.*

Keywords: European development, European mountain area, Eurostat indexes

1. Introduction

The mountain area is important for the mountain products quality, but especially because it provides about 60-80% of the planet's fresh water. FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2015) [8] classifies the mountain area according to the following scheme: • class 1: level $\geq 4,500$ m, • class 2: level 3,500–4,500 m • class 3: level 2,500– 3,500 m, • class 4: level 1,500–2,500 m and slope $\geq 2^\circ$, • class 5: level 1,000–1,500 m and slope $\geq 5^\circ$ or LER (local elevation range) > 300 m, • class 6: level 300–1,000 m and LER > 300 m. A seventh class, identified in 2002, includes isolated indoor basins and plateaus measuring less than 25 km² which are surrounded by mountains, but do not independently meet the criteria of the other classes [13].

Mountain area cover more than 40.6% of the European territory (Fig.1), representing 1,900,000 km² (19.1% of total population, approximately 94.3 million of people) [5].

The main reason of studying the mountain area is that it offers a healthier environment, with healthy fodder and animals contributing to the production of high quality food [17]. Mountain farming can only be achieved on a small scale, using sustainable local resources and thus conserving biodiversity [18].

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Fig. 1. Mountain surface in Europe

Source: European Commission, Mountain typology, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/RCI/#?vis=mountain.typology&lang=en>, [5].

The defining characteristics of mountain areas are determined by long distances or difficult access to certain points of interest, socio-economic and political marginalization, restrictions on access to infrastructure and urban areas, limited agricultural potential, limited possibilities for material or financial benefits. Numerous studies on mountain areas have been carried out over time. Some emphasize the adverse effects of climate change on mountain communities [2, 4, 10], others highlight the problems created by the natural handicap of these areas due to natural hazards and declining agricultural yields [14]. Mountain areas are subject of rapid socio-economic changes affecting agricultural systems as well as dietary patterns [3], [12], [14]. The importance of mountain areas on a global scale is reflected in the international agendas, most recently in the Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the United Nations. [3, 4], [9], [16].

2. Methodology

The paper present representative indexes for the European mountain regions, like *Area of the regions by other typologies; Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by other typologies; GDP from agriculture; GDP mountain region;*

National annual road freight transport by regions of loading, group of goods and other typologies; Community design (CD) applications per billion GDP by other typologies; Unemployment rates by sex, age and other typologies; Employment rates by sex, age and other typologies; Business demography and high growth enterprise by NACE Rev. 2 activity and other typologies; High-tech patent applications to the European patent office (EPO) by priority year and other typologies; Patent applications to the EPO by priority year, international patent classification (IPC) sections, classes and other typologies; European Union trade mark (EUTM) applications per billion GDP by other typologies. Data has been taken from Eurostat [7] and Trading Economics [15], and processed by the authors.

3. Results and discussions

The data of the paper show that indexes for mountain regions present important fluctuation between 2014-2018. Some data are extended to 2010-2018 period. For the index *Area of the regions by other typologies* (square kilometer – sq km) mountain regions of the Europe present surfaces as Belgium 1,164 km², Bulgaria 51,985 km², Czechia 15,708 km², Germany 40,849 km², Greece 119,779 km², Spain 279,865 km², France 134,694 km², Croatia 18,246 km², Italy 199,262 km², Austria 63,707 km², Poland 18,227 km², Portugal 31,913 km², Romania 92,297 km², Slovenia 16,766 km², Slovakia 36,492 km², United Kingdom 55,295 km², Iceland 102,679 km², Liechtenstein 160 km², Norway 263,461 km², Switzerland 40,260 km², Turkey 620,717 km². In 2010-2016 period the surface of some countries increased as follows: in Belgium by 0.08%, Italy 0.22%, Austria 5.56%, Portugal 0.008%, Romania 0.02%, Switzerland 0.008% and France 2.46% (2013-2016), while others decreased like: Bulgaria by -0.0001%, Czechia -25.67%, Greece -0.23%, Spain -0.003%, Slovakia -0.005%, United Kingdom -1.17%, Iceland -0.31%, Liechtenstein -0.31%, Norway -0.14% and Sweden -0.64% (2010-2012). As seen, the surface of European mountains has not remained the same during analyzed period. One of the causes was the erroneous measurement, but other reasons were geographical movements, environment disturbances, and so on. The surface of the European mountains is important in establishing an adequate agenda for a higher qualitative lifestyle. Mountains offer a higher qualitative air – water – soil system and are important factors for human health and food safety and security.

Regarding the index *Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by other typologies* (million euro) it should be reminded that between 2013–2017 period, that in some countries the general value of the GDP increased as follows: in Belgium by 8.52%, Bulgaria 25.27%, Slovenia 19.45%, Slovakia 15.31% and United Kingdom 7.95%. Between 2013-2016, the GDP value increased in

Belgium by 5.19%, Bulgaria 16.70%, Czechia 10.64%, Germany 11.70%, Spain 8.97%, Croatia 5.79%, Italy 4.19%, Austria 10.39%, Portugal 10.09%, Romania 20.48%, Slovenia 11.79%, Slovakia 9.95% and United Kingdom 12.76%, while in Greece it decreased by -1.22%. Regarding the GDP value (million euro) in the mountain regions, in 2016 it registered the following values: Belgium 5,169.16, Bulgaria 33,467.91, Czechia 25,564.36, Germany 229,306, Greece 109,092, Spain 702,130, France 404,324, Croatia 10,459.57, Italy 753,531.63, Austria 183,577.46, Poland 22,217.82, Portugal 40,247.01, Romania 48,736.9, Slovenia 33,669.35, Slovakia 40,364.81, United Kingdom 58,795.14. The GDP value for the mountain regions increased/decreased in the European countries, namely in Belgium by 21.62%, Bulgaria 6.41%, Czechia -14.36%, Germany -0.04%, Spain 22.78%, Croatia 15.43%, Italy -2.06%, Austria 22.20%, Romania -5.04%, Slovakia 24.14%, United Kingdom 4.99%, Norway -6.86% and Switzerland -271%. The main reason for the fluctuations has been the higher/lower advertising of the mountain products. The GDP from non-mountain regions (million euro) had the following values in 2016: Belgium 419,310.09, Bulgaria 14,660.73, Czechia 150,805.78, Denmark 278,734.86, Germany 2,930,448, Estonia 21,682.76, Greece 67,396, Spain 415,833, France 1,823,177, Croatia 36,179.86, Italy 934,893.84, Cyprus 18,490.2, Latvia 25,003.02, Lithuania 38,849.44, Luxembourg 53,303.03, Hungary 113,903.77, Malta 10,326.84, Netherlands 706,167, Austria 172,527.78, Poland 404,330.47, Portugal 146,084.92, Romania 121,538.55, Slovenia 6,687.86, Slovakia 40,861.26, Finland 216,053.57, Sweden 463,043.16, United Kingdom 2,325,107.81, Norway 57,270.37, Montenegro 3,954.2, North Macedonia 9,656.5, Albania 10,739.99, Serbia 36,698.52.

National annual road freight transport by regions of loading, group of goods and other typologies (thousand tones) is another important index for the mountain regions. The transportation in the mountain regions is realizing with difficulty, sometimes being almost impossible to access some important economical points. Between 2014-2018, total transported goods had the following fluctuations: Belgium 21.62%, Bulgaria 6.41%, Czechia -14.36%, Germany -0.03%, Spain 22.77%, Croatia 15.43%, Italy -2.05%, Austria 22.20%, Romania -5.04%, Slovakia 24.13%, United Kingdom 4.99%, Norway -6.85%, Switzerland -2.70%. In the same period, products of agriculture, hunting, and forestry; fish and other fishing products oscillates as follow: Belgium 248.38%, Bulgaria 22.80%, Czechia -27.57%, Spain 22.11%, Croatia -45.56%, Austria 25.63%, Romania -16.79%, Slovakia 33.59%, Norway 26.15%, Switzerland 5.99%.

Community design represents a set of rules created for the uniformization and protection of the industrial designs and creations across the [1], [6]. This is another important European mountain regions index. Between 2014-2018, Community design (CD) applications per billion GDP by other typologies (euro

per billion GDP), fluctuated for the mountain regions as follows: Belgium 94.20%, Czechia -9.21%. Between 2009-2013, this index decreased in Austria by -1,78%, between 2015-2007 in Poland it increased by 23.89%, in Sweden it decreased by -61.19%. Between 2013-2014, in Slovenia it increased by 2.17% and between 2008-2015 in Slovakia it also increased by 200%. At European level Belgium, Poland and Slovakia sustain mountain community design more than other countries, the effects being found in the exports volume of mountain products.

Between 2014-2018, the index *Unemployment rates by sex, age and other typologies*, for 15 to 24 years' segment of population, varied for the mountain regions as follows: Belgium -45.81%, Bulgaria -64.10%, Czechia -57.32%, Greece -23.80%, Spain -36.20%, France 1.36%, Italy -25.65%, Austria -20%, Poland -51.27%, Portugal -38.67%, Romania -23.50%, Slovenia -60.55%, Slovakia -43.03% and between 2016-2018, in Germany it decreased by -4.76%. The scenario for 2021 shows that unemployment will increase considerably, respectively in Belgium 6.5%, Bulgaria 8%, Czechia 5.5%, Greece 17.4%, Spain 17.2%, France 9.8%, Italy 11.1%, Austria 13.5%, Poland 7.6%, Portugal 8%, Romania 6.9%, Slovenia 9.5%, Slovakia 6.8%, Germany 3.8% [15]. The low rate of unemployment in the mountain area shows that mountain products are desired on the global market. The increasing unemployment shown by the forecasting represents an alarm signal for the decedents in order to invest more in mountain area of the Europe.

Economically active population by sex, age and other typologies (thousand persons) index, for 15 to 24 years' segment of population, fluctuated for the mountain regions between 2014-2018 as follows: Belgium -11.62%, Bulgaria -23.85%, Czechia -24.24%, Greece -15.67%, Spain -5.02%, Italy -7.83%, Austria -6.56%, Poland -8.25%, Portugal -6.41%, Romania -10.44%, Slovenia 11.11%, Slovakia -9.72%, United Kingdom -10.85%, while between 2016-2018 in Germany it increased by 1.42% and between 2017-2018 in France by 4.65%. The actual data show that entrepreneurship policies for the mountain area are not well sustained at the European level. More direct or indirect investments will better promote mountain products.

The index *Employment rates by sex, age and other typologies* (for 15 to 64 years) increased for the mountain regions between 2014-2018 as follows: Belgium 0.71%, Bulgaria 11.72%, Czechia 10.44%, Greece 11.49%, Spain 11.70%, Croatia 6.43%, Italy 5.26%, Austria 2.88%, Poland 9.84%, Portugal 10.83%, Romania 7.17%, Slovenia 11.31%, Slovakia 12.30%, United Kingdom 3.84% and between 2016-2018 in Germany by 1.29%. The increased employment rate for the European mountains area demonstrated that the high altitude environment becomes more friendly for people and entrepreneurs.

Business demography and high growth enterprise by NACE Rev. 2 activity and other typologies is one of the most important European index, presenting in the paper two important indicators, namely *Population of active enterprises in t – number* and *Persons employed in the population of active enterprises in t – number* for the sectors Industry, construction and services except insurance activities of holding companies; Industry (except construction); Construction; Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; Transportation and storage; Accommodation and food service activities; Information and communication; Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities except activities of holding companies; Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support service activities; Education, human health and social work activities; Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities.

Population of active enterprises in t – number, the main indicator of the entrepreneurship environment, presented an increased governance preoccupation for the European mountain area. For the sectors Industry, construction and services except insurance activities of holding companies it registered variations for Bulgaria 8.32%, Czechia 3.32%, Spain 3.96%, Croatia 3.30%, Italy -0.80%, Austria -3.38%, Portugal 3.95%, Romania 5.48%, and Slovakia 12.94%; Industry (except construction) for Bulgaria 4.09%, Czechia 7.04%, Spain -0.65%, Croatia -5.60%, Italy -4.01%, Austria -4.33%, Portugal 5.53%, Romania 2.66%, and Slovakia 9.14%; Construction for Bulgaria 5.80%, Czechia 8.26%, Spain -2.28%, Croatia -5.77%, Italy -8.33%, Austria -2.68%, Portugal -3.61%, Romania 7.38%, and Slovakia 12.23%; Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles for Bulgaria 1.84%, Czechia 7.28%, Spain 0.16%, Croatia -2.34%, Italy -4.72%, Austria -1.78%, Portugal -2.76%, Romania -1.13%, and Slovakia -1.76%; Transportation and storage for Bulgaria 19.35%, Czechia -0.58%, Spain -4.96%, Croatia -2.77%, Italy -6.09%, Austria -4.21%, Portugal -5.22%, Romania 15.68%, and Slovakia 11.55%; Accommodation and food service activities for Bulgaria 4.65%, Czechia -6.83%, Spain 0.53%, Croatia 15.86%, Italy 1.64%, Austria -13.69%, Portugal 7.32%, Romania 7.59%, Slovakia 6.01%; Information and communication for Bulgaria 26.71%, Czechia 39.01%, Spain 14.79%, Croatia 7.24%, Italy 5.52%, Austria 1.15%, Portugal 12.45%, Romania 3.79%, Slovakia 28.29%; Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities except activities of holding companies for Bulgaria 13.36%, Czechia -26.04%, Spain 19.10%, Croatia 7.20%, Italy 1.60%, Austria -19.58%, Portugal 2.87%, Romania 20.28%, and Slovakia 53.36%; Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support service activities for Bulgaria 15.93%, Czechia 9.45%, Spain 6.47%, Croatia 10.11%, Italy 4.83%, Austria -4.64%, Portugal 13.31%, Romania 3.12% and Slovakia 30.99%; Education; human health and social work activities for Bulgaria 5.77%, Czechia 1.36%, Spain 14.89%, Croatia 31.70%,

Italy 11.97%, Austria 10.92%, Portugal 3.27%, Romania 29.31%, and Slovakia 17.25%; Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities for Bulgaria 14.31%, Czechia -6.54%, Spain 14.33%, Croatia -7.30%, Italy 3.78%, Austria -2.22%, Portugal 11.57%, Romania 19.27% and Slovakia 37.07%.

Persons employed in the population of active enterprises in t – number, one of the most important socio-economic indicator, show for the European mountain area an increasing concern from the community space governments. The analyzed sector presented lower variations, but the general business environment was favorable to the mountain area, respectively for: Industry, construction and services, except insurance activities of holding companies showed fluctuations for Bulgaria 3.37%, Czechia -2.30%, Spain 7.56%, Croatia -0.35%, Italy 0.29%, Austria 2.37%, Romania 8.54%, and Slovakia 5.07%; Industry (except construction) for Bulgaria 4.35%, Czechia 4.42%, Spain 6.84%, Croatia -8.87%, Italy -1.18%, Austria 2.38%, Romania 5.68%, and Slovakia 8.17%; Construction for Bulgaria 0.14%, Czechia 3.60%, Spain -0.76%, Croatia -3.56%, Italy -9.96%, Austria 0.49%, Portugal 1.11%, Romania 1.89%, and Slovakia 4.18; Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles for Bulgaria 2.33%, Czechia 2.64%, Spain 6.51%, Croatia -3.42%, Italy -2.34%, Austria 1.33%, Portugal 3.83%, Romania 6.89%, and Slovakia 0.29%; Transportation and storage for Bulgaria 8.88%, Czechia 6.75%, Spain 6.56%, Croatia 2.47%, Italy 8.82%, Austria 6.74%, Romania 22.25%, and Slovakia 5.84%; Accommodation and food service activities for Bulgaria 3.42%, Czechia -3.47%, Spain 13.67%, Croatia 6.33%, Italy 3.75%, Austria 2.38%, Portugal 11.59%, Romania 14.06, and Slovakia 8.78%; Information and communication for Bulgaria 16.86%, Czechia -7.33%, Spain 18.87%, Croatia 9.60%, Italy 6.69, Austria 11.67, Portugal 27.53, Romania 21.71%, and Slovakia 32.36%; Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities except activities of holding companies for Bulgaria -5.69%, Czechia -29.48%, Spain -0.70%, Croatia -0.35%, Italy -2.53%, Austria -10.32%, Portugal -8.81%, Romania 10.84%, and Slovakia 25.13%; Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support service activities for Bulgaria 7.70%, Czechia -12.21%, Spain 8.14%, Croatia 2.99%, Italy 4.95%, Austria 3.51%, Portugal 14.42%, Romania 9.38%, and Slovakia 20.49%; Education, human health and social work activities for Bulgaria -2.03%, Czechia -29.49%, Spain 11.19%, Croatia 30.06%, Italy 10.49%, Austria 8.68%, Romania 25.48%, and Slovakia -38.60%; Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities for Bulgaria -1.75%, Czechia -12.97%, Spain 17.10%, Croatia 10.44%, Italy 3.69%, Austria 1.37%, Portugal 11.60%, Romania 20.53%, and Slovakia 30.87%.

Specific for Romania, it must be reminded that the mountain area covers 90.24 thousands km² (37.9% of the total area of the country), the population being 5,535,706 people (24.9% of the total population). "Romania - with the largest

mountain range in Europe located inside a country - did not support collectivization in the mountains, but remained with a very low level of technology in peasant households. Post-1990 economic phenomena, including excessive liberalism, with ridiculous prices for mountain products, milk and meat, raw materials, the collapse of the price of wool, outside the protective control of the state and intensely polarized economic interests, other conjunctural elements (focus exclusively on large agricultural restrictions, unrestricted and uncompensated restrictive measures for livestock farmers, industrial and job dissolution, or objectives (lack of knowledge, lack of expertise in the field, lack of specialists, research, the lack of models, as well as the size of the mountainous territory and the financial austerity of the moment, the lack of awareness and insufficient political will, etc.), opening the borders for lib it was a movement of people - there was a phenomenon of violent rural exodus, accentuated after Romania's accession to the European Union" [11].

Conclusions

- (1) Analyzed data, the statics of the paper, show that European countries have extensively invested in the mountain area in the last years. *Business demography and high growth enterprise* present a strong asset for the entrepreneurship of the European mountain regions. Due to a coherent policy, unemployment has been decreased and employment grew up. Forecasting show that if the investment policies will not continue, then the analyzed indices will have lower and lower values.
- (2) The surface of the European mountains is important in establishing an adequate agenda for higher qualitative lifestyle. Mountains offer higher qualitative air – water – soil system and are important factors for human health and food safety and security.
- (3) Mountain living and entrepreneurship is strongly influenced by the infrastructure and geographical realities. Governments should take into consideration higher investments in these sectors. The defining characteristics of mountain areas are determined by long distances or difficult access to certain points of interest, socio-economic and political marginalization, restrictions on access to infrastructure and urban areas, limited agricultural potential, limited possibilities for material or financial benefits.
- (4) Mountain area is important because the ecosystem and the environment of this area affect its food system. High altitude areas (mountains) are less polluted than low altitude areas (plains). In mountainous areas agriculture is intensively practiced. Farmers are poorly integrated in commodity markets and it is difficult to compete on a large scale with producers in large-scale plains. The only solution

for mountain producers is to produce high quality food. The mountain products market has the features of an emerging market, ensuring products with superior nutritional values, healthier and high organic character. This emerging market, the mountain area, offers opportunities for the development of sustainable value chains, ensuring opportunities for acquisition by all the people.

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CONDITIONS AND TRENDS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECOLOGICAL AGRI-FOOD MARKET IN ROMANIA IN PANDEMIC CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *In the current stage of the pandemic period, the use of SWOT analysis becomes a specific for investigating and assessing the situation of the organic agri-food market. The paper follows the structural specificity of the SWOT method. The aspects captured can be considered challenges in the area of organic agri-food market with references to the general framework of economic development through interpretative forms that were reproduced: at territorial level (local, regional and national form), along with the aspect of their importance (primary, secondary and auxiliary). At the same time, the bivalence of knowing the influence of the pandemic on the impulses of the ecological agri-food market was considered by: the quantitative aspect (which referred to the capture of the structural conditions nominated by the SWOT analysis) and the qualitative aspect (through which the manifestation of the conjunctural relations in the chain of the ecological agri-food market to be framed by degrees of intensity). The set of conditions presented foresees the tendency to introduce cyber mechanisms that can be appropriate forms of knowledge of some challenges signaled by the use of SWOT analysis. This is because the contouring of the feedback circuits through which the output sizes of the regulated system act differently on the regulatory system and in the current situation of the ecological agri-food market in pandemic conditions. By performing/transposing the coordinates specific to the SWOT analysis, the problems investigated can be identified by the agents themselves interested in the market. The explanatory extension provided by the SWOT analysis showed that even in the current situation of the organic agri-food market in pandemic conditions, the existence of a structural delimitation can also be represented by a cybernetic system [Ecological market level (pandemic conditions) = $f(S, W, O, T)$]. It appears the existence of a high degree of uncertainty on the market. The correlative set of the four parameters can be expressed mathematically in a generic functional form of the type $\rightarrow \square + S \cdot W \cdot O / T$). Even in pandemic conditions, according to this mathematical correlative formulation: strengths and weaknesses represent what exists, respectively the challenges posed by these parameters considered: descriptive, respectively impulses of organic agri-food market functions, and opportunities and threats reflect what should be had in view, in the options involved in the mechanisms of market functioning.*

Keywords: SWOT analysis, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats. ecological market, pandemic (COVID-19 crisis), agro-ecological vocation

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1. Introduction

In the current stage of the pandemic period, the use of SWOT analysis becomes a specific method of investigation and assessment and to know the situation of the organic agri-food market. The aim of the paper was to present this problem through the specific structural elements of the SWOT method.

The captured aspects can be considered challenges within the area of the ecological agri-food market with references on the general framework of economic development: at territorial level, together with the aspect of their importance (main, secondary and auxiliary) [15].

At the same time, the bivalence of knowing the influence of the pandemic on the impulses of the ecological agri-food market was considered through: the quantitative side (through the methodological structures of the SWOT analysis) and the qualitative side (through which the conjuncture relations framed by degrees of intensity) [2].

By performing/transposing the specific coordinates of the SWOT analysis, problems investigated or even initially outlined can be identified by the agents themselves interested in the market.

2. Materials and methods

Adequate to highlight the current situation of the organic agri-food market in pandemic conditions in the paper was used a methodological form expressed by SWOT analysis.

Answers were sought in the form of explanatory and tabular texts with reference to the knowledge of objective and subjective causes that acted on the mechanism of this market of organic agri-food products in the three main stages of the chain but appropriate to the area of existence of the crisis COVID-19 .

The forms of information were paraphrased by SWOT analysis according to the name and structural classification using abbreviations given by the following terms [1] [4]: Strengths, qualities that in market conditions may be tangible or intangible that, allowing it to perform its functions; Weaknesses, which are the elements that prevent the fulfillment of market functions (which can be minimized or eliminated); Opportunities, the conditions under which the organic agri-food market can benefit in order to become more profitable (competitive advantage from capitalizing on opportunities) for economic operators in the supply chain; Threats, extremely dangerous environmental conditions which may jeopardize on the one hand the proper functioning of the market (through its mechanisms) and, on the other hand, the profitability of economic operators (with regard to their stability and survival).

Methodologically, a structural delimitation was used in the whole paper, which can be given by a cybernetic system [9], [12] Ecological market level (pandemic conditions) = $f(S, W, O, T)$. It was found the existence of a high degree of uncertainty on the market, which is why the correlative set of those parameters can be expressed mathematically in a generic functional form of the type $\rightarrow (+ S - W \cdot O/T)$. In this mathematical formulation the strengths and weaknesses represent what exists, respectively the level of these parameters considered descriptive for the organic agri-food market, and the opportunities and threats reflect what will be and is considered, the choices to be made by the people involved in the planning process [3] [4] [10, 11, 13].

Structurally-synthetically, the study aimed to capture/signal those conditions through the territorial background of pandemic manifestation through the problems outlined by the SWOT methodology, in the trivalence of the flow of the main stages of the ecological market (production-distribution-consumption), to outline/substantiate the most appropriate market strategies.

3. Results and discussions

The paper seeks to outline the realization of assumptions for the current situation of the organic agri-food market on which in the conditions of pandemic manifestation at present the knowledge in this field is less detailed.

In this respect, the SWOT analysis is a real tool through which the overall analysis of the position of the organic agri-food market in the current conditions of the COVID-19 crisis can be made. The challenges arising from the SWOT analysis can assess the internal potential and the limits of possible opportunities / threats from the external environment, thus being able to outline the most appropriate strategies of the organic agri-food market in pandemic conditions [9].

Thus, for the current and perspective knowledge of those links (SWOT) adapted to the flow of the ecological agri-food market, investigations were carried out in which the study followed: the response reactions/challenges that were presented at the level of the territorial structure (by local, regional and national form) through a micro and macro territorial level (the interpretative forms being rendered territorially through the local, regional and national form), but also of the degree of importance of these conditionings (main, secondary, auxiliary).

3.1. Conditionings of the ecological production system according to the SWOT analysis

Were outlined based on the structure of local, regional and national areas but also according to the territorial vocation. Indeed, in the conditions of the pandemic, the

structure of the conditionings was deepened in a form specific to the vocation of the sphere of the territorial ecological production system (territorial, economic and social agro-ecological) and which are presented succinctly in Tables 1-a and 1-b.

Table 1a. Ecological production system conditions rendered by SWOT analysis (strengths, opportunities)

The internal environment	Manifestation activities	External environment
Strengths		Opportunities
1. The presence on the Romanian territory of all forms of relief - mountains, hills, plateaus, depressions, valleys and plains; agroecosystems suitable for all organic production systems; balanced ratio as area between the main landforms.	Territorial agro-ecological vocation	Taking advantage of local, national and international economic situations; the introduction and application of structural and functional forms favorable to organic farming systems, the intensification of measures to implement the CAP to green agriculture;
2. Continuous growth of the surface of agricultural land and arable land cultivated in ecological system; zoning of organic production, corresponding to the supply of soil, climate and specialized labor force; subsidies/aid for organic farming; conversion support; low level of chemical fertilizers.	Economic	Subsidizing organic agricultural production; increasing and diversifying demand; the multifunctional character of ecological systems; improving technologies for the use of renewable energy sources; stimulating agricultural workers returning home from the diaspora; setting up financial instruments for small farms and agricultural SMEs; financing the modernization of canneries
3. Simplification of the CAP and flexibility measures, the existing level of the agricultural workforce; the existence of experience in organic farming and their desire to improve their knowledge; direct support for farmers and rural areas (loans or guarantees to cover operating costs, flexibility in the use of financial instruments dedicated to rural development; increase in advance payments	Social	The large number of organizations and individuals involved in organic farming; cheap labor; exchange of information / knowledge and experience; variation in the degree of COVID -19 infestation and the incidence of other incurable human diseases that will increase the demand for organic products; increasing people's living standards; intensifying movements for healthy eating; increasing the number of research and innovation programs and projects on organic farming;

Source: [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [12], [14].

Table 1b. Ecological production system conditions rendered by SWOT analysis (weaknesses, threats)

The internal environment	Manifestation activities	External environment
Weaknesses		Threats
1. Degradation of cultivated agricultural lands in ecological system; diminishing biodiversity; non-compliance with production activities in compliance with the objectives of the Technical Inspection in the field of organic farming. Deficient aspects in the collection of organic horticultural products, can be included in a specialized aspect that can be added from specialized farms in companies for processing that are related to: financial difficulties of factories; low demand for canned vegetables and fruits; competition from imported products; the low quality of canned vegetables and fruits and their poor promotion; reduced exports of canned vegetables and fruits to foreign markets.	Territorial agro-ecological vocation	Global warming above the normal limit; increasing the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events; the sometimes-irreversible change in the composition of flora and fauna.
2. Small areas under organic farming, inputs and technologies inadequate to organic farming rules; delivery of small and inhomogeneous quantities of organic products, obtained on areas with low yields.	Economic	The financial recession and its symptoms; contamination of organic agricultural and food products with genetically modified organisms and pesticides, economic fraud.
3. Labor force at a lower and lower level, the high level of self-consumption of organic production corresponding to the particularities of organic agriculture and the cultivation area; date sources; lack of professionalism in administration in all forms of education; the existence of the potential to be developed in organic farming; lack of initiatives in setting up non-governmental organizations in this field.	Social	Aging of agricultural producers; depopulation of villages and communes; the sharp decrease / disappearance of the number of small farms; bureaucracy in administrative and control structures, profile; declining consumer confidence in organic farming; the negative attitude of some representatives of the media and conventional agriculture; European legislation for organic production; the policy of supporting producers which did not always have the expected effects; non-compliance by operators with the rules on production, processing, packaging, transport, storage, distribution and import from third countries of organic products; lack of operator documents, respectively of mandatory registrations; supporting the digitization of the sale of production by small farmers; additional and more flexible funding for short chain cooperation projects.

Source: [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [14].

3.2. Regarding the conditions for the distribution of organic production

The SWOT analysis is considered to be of particular importance in the organic market. It can be said that even in the conditions of the pandemic an analysis in this phase of distribution is focused on degrees of importance of the main secondary and auxiliary activities. The flow of activities for the current conditions can be detailed by coordinates that are summarized in Table 2-a and 2-b.

Table 2a. Conditions for the distribution of ecological production rendered by SWOT analysis (strengths, opportunities)

The internal environment	The activities intensity degree	External environment
Strengths		Opportunities
1. Growing demand for organic products in the EU; expanding the capacity of zonal markets for national agri-food products; structurally-organizationally adapted forms of wholesale markets for forms of distribution	Main	1. The trend of setting up a "green hall"; developing retail markets through which market segments can expand; increasing the demand for quality in green markets; creating / maintaining an efficient organic food supply chain; fiscal facilities in case of creating a large number of jobs and obtaining non-reimbursable financing; elaboration and implementation of programs to promote the consumption of ecological products; a strategic location of access to the green markets that have been subjected to the pandemic; capitalizing on market opportunities / proposals that can be included in EU rules
2. An increasing degree of sales force liberalization; the possibility of implementing the current forms but also of some adequate forms of distribution of ecological products; the existence of a wide range of market outlets that farmers can turn to; implementation of specific forms in retail distribution; certain possibilities to expand the area of the organic market to other urban areas or crowded centers; organization of marketing cooperatives, but also of encouraging a number of forms of distribution; amplifying the range of products offered to consumers; construction of warehouses for the storage of perishable ecological products; the existence of already organized marketing systems for organic products	Auxiliary	2. Rhythmic supply of the market with ecological products through which speculative intermediaries can be eliminated; entering a new or still unexploited market; possibilities for setting up collection centers; capitalizing on opportunities in the foreign market; the existence of a short market channel; possibilities to update the door of an existing contracting system according to the current conditions; reducing the number of field inspections

Source: [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [14].

Table 2b. Ecological production distribution conditions rendered by SWOT analysis
(weaknesses, threats)

The internal environment	The activities intensity degree	External environment
Weaknesses		Threats
1. Low level of labor, poorly qualified management; outdated equipment; disproportionate production capacities of large distributors / processors; some organic products have deficient trade balances; the major lack of orientation towards certain market forms of many producers; low economic performance; the lack of a stable collection system	Main	1. Prolongation of the pandemic period that will influence the economic crisis; deficiencies in compliance with quality standards; changes in tax legislation related to a low predictability of the business environment; existing deficiencies in the creation and operation of marketing infrastructures; the loss of foreign markets and the reduced capitalization of Romania's potential
2. Organic products obtained in farms are intended primarily for self-consumption; small quantities of organic products still sold for processing to collection centers; the situations of market movements created by the pandemic generate competitiveness is reduced compared to competition from imported products;	Secondary	2. Poor organization of agricultural markets, lack of information on export opportunities; deficient structure of exports of organic products; the penetration of imports into the internal ecological market; the financial blockage present on the entire supply chain; diminishing the purchasing power of consumers; formation / existence of a distribution channel too long; competition from supermarkets; threatening small producers by expanding hypermarkets.
3. Existence of unused spaces; inappropriate behavior of distributors with the agricultural producer and consumer; the absence of programs for the marketing of organic products in pandemic conditions; partial or total non-application of EU regulations	Auxiliary	3. Fragmentation of the wholesale distribution system; instability of the internal supply; competition through the import of organic agri-food products; a lower level of retail prices for small-scale organic products

Source: [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [14].

3.3. Regarding the conditioning of the consumption of the ecological production according to the SWOT analysis that is permanently manifested within the agri-food chain.

It can be nominated as one of the most important stages and for the conditions of the pandemic period. The delimitation given by the SWOT structure at which a deepening is performed through the main, secondary and auxiliary framing degrees.

Such an analysis of the consumption of organic production for the current conditions of the COVID -19 crisis can be delimited by coordinates that are summarized in Table 3-a and 3-b.

Table 3a. Conditioning the consumption of organic production according to the SWOT analysis (strong bridge, opportunities)

The internal environment	The activities intensity degree	External environment
Strengths		Opportunities
Increasing demand for green pandemic consumption in the EU; raising consumer awareness of the consumption of organic products	Main	Changes in consumer preferences; development of access infrastructure for ecological products; tax facilities in case of creating a large number of jobs; favored consumption as a result of obtaining non-reimbursable financing; entering new markets or markets not yet exploited;
The rules of social distance applied during the pandemic; improvements in the forms of organic agri-food consumption.	Secondary	The tendency to increase consumption focused on forms of behavior; enhancing the "cleaner production" approach; increase the volume of purchases
The motivations arising from the diversification of the forms of consumption of ecological agri-food products in the conditions of the pandemic; possibilities for the consumer to investigate the markets	Auxiliary	Amplified availability in the consumption of organic products; imposing requirements on the certification of organic products by consumers; development of ecological tourism potential; new forms of consumer purchase of products; expenditures for organic agri-food products; the definite trend of online shopping growth;

Source: [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [11] [14].

Table 3b. Consumption conditions of organic production according to SWOT analysis
(weaknesses, threats)

The internal environment	The activities intensity degree	External environment
Weaknesses		Threats
Relatively low level of investment in the trade of medium-sized organic products; lack of coordination in consumer behavior of organic products; limitations created by consumer behavior to develop viable project proposals.	Main	Difficulties in supporting the investment costs of the projects: organizational, political and financial nature; manifestations reported in the supplier-customer relationship inconsistent with the forms of organization included in the EU Directives
Relatively low level of investment in the retail network; the limited capacity of actual consumers to develop viable project proposals;	Secondary	Increased pressure through consumer behavior on biodiversity and quality of agri-food products; the possibility of high cost levels; inappropriate use of EU funds; changes in consumer preferences;
Partial lack of state interventions in / through improper practice of ecological terms; the non-existence of the establishment of contraventions for acts of fraud in the control-consumption relationship	Auxiliary	Partial/total lack of cross-sectoral communication and coordination in consumption; the impossibility of securing and controlling the consumer's purchases on the market.

Source: [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [11] [14].

It follows the need to know events, actual operation of the production, distribution and consumption which surprised SWOT analysis and national pandemic conditions, those specific response elements in the food market flow.

Regarding the conditions captured in the market of organic agri-food products in Romania, it can be said that they are directly related to the forms and intensity of the instability of the pandemic period. But at the same time there is a need to follow the very forms of existence and intensity of the COVID-19 crisis (in line with the level of relaxation of restrictive measures).

Respectively, following the manifestations of the consumer's behavior of organic agri-food products, it can be outlined through forms of scenarios. These and in the case of organic agri-food consumption systems in pandemic condition, it can be presented by adapting those in the specialty literature [11]:

- return to normal (with reference to the level of expenditures that may remain unchanged in pandemic conditions);

- cautious, but extravagant (spending is higher in areas considered more important for high-income consumers);
- maintaining an economic level (where consumer spending is pessimistic about the future);
- continuing to reduce costs (consumers make spending cuts because the greatest risk could be represented by job loss);
- the return to a high employment potential of the young generation (currently there is optimism even if food consumption has been disrupted in their daily lives).

Conclusions

The aim of this paper was to highlight a possible knowledge of the short-term level of the market for organic agri-food products in the event of a pandemic (created by the COVID-19 crisis).

(1) Structurally methodologically through the SWOT analysis, references were made to: (i) delimiting the strong points that can be transformed into competitive advantages; (ii) weaknesses that need to be identified in a causal and attenuated analytical form; (iii) opportunities from the external environment to be exploited in the market area; (iv) identifying threats at the right time to enable strategies to respond or adapt to the environment of the organic agri-food market and in pandemic conditions.

(2) In the realization/transposition of the coordinates specific to the SWOT analysis, the investigated problems for the ecological agri-food market in pandemic conditions it is necessary to know the following tendencies: (i) the tendency to extend the favorable form of strengths; (ii) the tendency to diminish/ hide weaknesses; (iii) the possibility of assimilation and/or confusion between the optimistic sides regarding the strengths/opportunities and the pessimistic ones regarding the weaknesses/threats; (iv) performing the SWOT analysis which must be permanently correlated with the actual desire for action.

(3) From the conditions presented, trends can be outlined for the application and in the case of the organic agri-food market, being suggested that the SWOT analysis be accompanied by SMART objectives. They can be reproduced according to the following structure (which may be appropriate even in pandemic conditions): specific; measurable; affordable / accessible; relevant; term of execution.

(4) The synthetic opinions on consumer behavior presented in the scenarios form highlight the possibility of predicted forms of consumption level that may occur in the agri-food market for organic products. By introducing cyber mechanisms into all these conditionings, appropriate forms of knowledge of emerging trends can be established using SWOT analysis.

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VARIATION OF THE AGRICULTURAL CROPS YIELD DUE TO CLIMATE CHANGE IN CONSTANTA COUNTY COMPARED TO DOBROGEA REGION AND ROMANIA IN THE PERIOD 2010-2019

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Abstract. *The study aimed to analyze the evolution of cultivated surface and yields achieved by the main agricultural crops: wheat, barley, maize, sunflower and rape in Constanta County compared to the yields carried out in Dobrogea Region and in Romania in the period 2010-2019. The climate change especially in terms of higher and higher temperatures, lower and lower amount of precipitations and severe, strong and long length drought were considered responsible of the decline of average production per surface unit in the analyzed period. The results proved that in Constanta County, wheat and maize recorded a high performance compared to the regional decade average and the national decade average. In case of maize crop, Constanta County registered lower yields in almost all the years except 2010 and 2011, both compared to the level in Dobrogea region and in Romania. In case of sunflower crop, in Constanta County, yields were much lower in almost all the years compared to the performance achieved in the Dobrogea region, except 2017 and 2018. Also, rape crop achieved a decline of production per ha in Constanta County compared to the performance in the region of Dobrogea in almost all the years, except 2010 and 2012. For diminishing the effects of climate change on the agriculture of Dobrogea region and especially of Constanta County, farmers have to continue to adapt production technologies, using cultivars and hibrids highly resistant to drought, diseases and pests, choosing a sowing period adapted to the temperature and water reserve into the soil, a corresponding fertilization and plant protection to achieve the desired yields. Also, the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development has to urgently implement the program for sustaining agriculture in Dobrogea region recovering the irrigation systems essential for avoiding aridization of the area.*

Keywords: wheat, barley, maize, sunflower, rape, yield, drought, Constanta County

1. Introduction

Cereals and oil seeds plants are the main groups of crops which play an important role in Romania's agriculture (Popescu Agatha, 2012a, 2012b, 2012c, 2015a, 2015b, 2017) [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

Romania is not only an major producer of cereals and oil seeds but also one of the key exporting member state of the EU.

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Cereals and oil seeds plants are cultivated on the large surfaces and mainly in the South Muntenia, South East, South West and West part of the country (Popescu Agatha, 2018a, 2018b, 2020) [15, 16, 17].

Constanta County and Dobrogea area play an important role in Romania's agriculture. In 2019, in Constanta County, there were cultivated 476,680 ha by 4.57% less than in 2010, and this trend does not fit the general ascending tendency in Romania's cultivated area which accounted for 8,737,275 ha in 2019, being by 11,91% higher than at the beginning of the last decade.

Therefore, the share of Constanta County in Romania's cultivated area declined from 6.39% in 2010 to 5.45% in 2019 (NIS, 2020) [8].

The main agricultural plants cultivated in Constanta County are wheat, barley, maize, sunflower and rape whose cropped surface, all together, in 2019 accounted for 402,247 ha, representing 84.38% of the whole cultivated surface in the area. While the surface cultivated with wheat registered a slight increase, maize was cultivated on a 2.18 times larger surface than in 2010 and sunflower on an area by 11.29% higher than in the first year of the decade. An important decline in the cultivated area was noticed in case of barley (-1.57 percentage points) and mainly in case of rape (- 11.77 percentage points) (Tabel 1).

Table 1. Cultivated area with the main agricultural crops and their share in the cultivated area in Constanta County in 2019 versus 2010

		Wheat	Barley	Maize	Sunflower	Rape
Cultivated area (ha)	2010	180,514	55,055	28,889	78,014	80,168
	2019	181,623	45,092	63,499	86,828	25,205
Share in cultivated area in Constanta county (%)	2010	36.14	11.02	5.78	15.61	16.05
	2019	37.89	9.45	13.32	18.21	4.28

Source: Own calculation nased on the data from NIS, 2020 [8].

These changes in Constanta County agricultural crops structure are closely related to the importance of each crop, its productivity level, the favorability of soil type, climate conditions, market price volatility at the farm gate.

However, climate change impact on agricultural production is more visible year by year in Romania, and especially in Dobrogea region and Constanta County.

As in Dobrogea region, the annual average temperature is much over 11⁰C and the amount of precipitations varies between 351 and 450 mm/year, it is considered that this South East part of Romania has a high level of drought risk (Mateescu Elena, 2016) [6].

Year by year, Constanta County is facing increased temperatures, the decline of rainfalls, water deficit into the soil, a long period of drought, the tendency to aridization and desrtification which destroy soil structure, fertility and

productivity (Prăvălie et al, 2014, Prăvălie and Bandoc, 2015, Sandu et al., 2010) [18, 19, 20].

During the last decade, 2010-2019, the extreme droughts were registered in the years 2011-2012, 2014-2015, 2016, 2018, and 2019. The year 2019 was an atypical one, characterized by a long and severe drought which started in spring, continued in summer, autumn, and in winter, then in spring, summer and autumn of the year 2020. For this reason, it was named "the warmest year since measurements are made in Romania, that is during the last 140 years since 1900 till present" (Mateescu et al, 2009, Mateescu, 2016, Mateescu, 2019) [4, 5, 6].

Facing with drought during the last decades, farmers have learned from their own experience and using the research results regarding how to fight against drought by adapting production technologies, they found solutions year by year trying to diminish the negative effects of this terrible phenomenon which affect agriculture in Constanta County and in Dobrogea region (Manole et al., 2018a, 2018 b, 2018c) [2, 3, 4].

However, the insufficient irrigated agricultural surface in Constanta County, which accounts nowadays for only 13,000 ha compared to 421,319 irrigated arable land in 1990, and in addition the lack of protective forestry curtains, have amplified the effects of the drought on agricultural production performance, environment, biosystem, and farmers' income (Ciobanu Diana, 2020) [1].

The purposes of this study were: (i) to study the dynamics of yields of the main agricultural crops: wheat, barley, maize, sunflower and rape in Constanta County in the decade 2010-2019 in order to identify the main trends; (ii) to compare the average decade yield in Constanta County with the average decade yield achieved in Dobrogea region and in Romania in order to quantify the differences which have to prove the effect of drought; (iii) to evaluate the annual losses of yield in Constanta County from the yield level in Dobrogea region and at the national level and (iv) to establish the suitable recommendations that farmers and authorities have to follow to diminish the effects of drought in Constanta County.

2. Materials and Methods

The study is based on the empirical data collected from National Institute of Statistics, 2020 and are processed using the following methodology:

The average value of agricultural crop production during the decade 2010-2019 which was calculated with the formula:

$$\bar{y} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n y^t}{n}$$

$$\text{Mean at the decade level, } \bar{Y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n}$$

Absolute differences between average decade yield in Constanta County, Dobrogea region and Romania, $\Delta = \bar{y}_{CT} - \bar{y}_{Dobrogea}$; $\Delta = \bar{y}_{CT} - \bar{y}_{Romania}$;

Absolute differences between average crop yield in Constanta County, Dobrogea region and Romania, $\Delta = y_{CT} - y_{Dobrogea}$; $\Delta = y_{CT} - y_{Romania}$.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Yield level for the main agricultural crops in Constanta County

In the analyzed decade, in Constanta County, agricultural yields increased for all the crops in 2019 compared to 2010 by + 80.8% for wheat, by +63.14% for barley, by+14.27% for maize, by + 72.95% for sunflower and by +13.38% for rape.

The lowest yields were recorded especially in the year 2012 for barley 2,674 kg/ha, for maize 1.430 kg/ha and for sunflower 1,126 kg/ha. In 2010, wheat registered the smallest yield 2,626 kg/ha and in 2011, rape 1,342 kg/ha (Table 2).

Table 2. Yields for the main agricultural crops in Constanta County, 2010-2019 (kg/ha)

	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Sunflower	Rape
2010	2,626	2,914	4,925	1,538	1,875
2011	4,307	4,036	5,025	1,343	1,342
2012	3,039	2,674	1,430	1,126	1,690
2013	2,921	2,836	3,273	1,495	1,720
2014	3,279	3,063	3,575	1,834	2,167
2015	3,785	4,176	2,894	1,597	2,301
2016	4,008	4,617	3,191	1,502	2,293
2017	5,413	4,475	5,786	3,180	2,211
2018	5,677	5,207	8,124	3,715	2,288
2019	4,748	4,754	5,628	2,660	2,126
2019/2010 %	180.80	163.14	114.27	172.95	113.38
Decade Mean	3,980.3	3,875.2	4,385.1	1,999	2,001.3

Source: Own calculations based on the data from NIS, 2020 [8].

The highest grain yields were achieved in the year 2018: 5,677 kg/ha wheat, 5,207 kg/ha barley, 8,124 kg/ha maize, 3,715 kg/ha sunflower seeds and in 2015, 2,288 kg/ha rape seeds.

In the studied decade, the average production per surface unit was: 3,980.3 kg/ha wheat, 3,875 kg/ha barley, 4,385.1 kg/ha maize, 1,999 kg/ha sunflower and 2,001.3 kg/ha rape. Therefore, maize is a high performance crop, followed by wheat and barley, while rape and sunflower have a lower productivity (Table 2).

3.2. Comparison between the average yield achieved in the period 2010-2019 by Constanta County and the average decade yield in Dobrogea region and in Romania

In the last decade, Constanta County carried out a higher production performance in case of wheat and barley than the decade average in Dobrogea region and at the national level.

In case of maize, Constanta County achieved a decade average by - 414.7 kg/ha lower compared to the national level and by -98.7 kg/ha lower compared to the regional level.

In case of sunflower, the decade average was by -135.6 kg/ha smaller than the decade average in Romania and by +83.4 kg/ha higher compared to the regional average (Table 3).

Table 3. Average decade yields for the main agricultural crops in Constanta County, compared to Dobrogea region and Romania's performance, 2010-2019 (kg/ha)

	Wheat	Barley	Maize	Sunflower	Rape
Constanta county	3,980.3	3,875.2	4,385.1	1,999	2,001.3
Dobrogea region	3,713.4	3,281.0	4,483.8	1,915.6	1,911.2
Romania	3,821.5	3,449.2	4,799.8	2,134.6	2,308.7
Difference versus Romania	+158.8	+426	-414.7	-135.6	-307.4
Difference versus Dobrogea region	+266.9	+594.2	-98.7	+83.4	+90.1

Source: Own calculation based on the data from NIS, 2020 [8].

In case of rape, in Constanta County, the decade average yield was by -307.4 kg/ha lower than the national average and by +90.1 kg/ha higher than the decade average in Dobrogea region.

This proves that during the analyzed decade, the climate conditions affected very much agricultural yield in Constanta County in case of maize, which was not a

competitive crop both at the regional and the national level, having a lower productivity.

Sunflower and rape have also registered a lower productivity in Constanta County (Table 3).

3.3. Differences regarding maize crop yield versus the yield in Dobrogea region and Romania

Compared to the average production in Dobrogea region, maize yield in Constanta County was lower in the years 2013, 2014, 2018, 2017, 2015, 2016, which are the unfavorable years for this crop in this area. The yield losses varied between -579 kg/ha in 2013 and -20 kg/ha in 2016. The best agricultural year in Constanta County compared to the average maize yield at the regional level was 2019 (Table 4).

Table 4. Differences in maize yield in Constanta County compared to the yield in Dobrogea region and Romania, 2010-2019 (kg/ha)

	Maize Yield (Kg/ha)			Differences between Constanta County and	
	Constanta County	Dobrogea Region	Romania	Dobrogea Region	Romania
2010	4,925	4,237	4,309	+688	+616
2011	5,025	4,541	4,525	+484	+500
2012	1,430	1,374	2,180	+56	-750
2013	3,273	3,852	4,488	-579	-1,215
2014	3,575	4,143	4,770	-557	-1,195
2015	2,894	2,980	3,462	-86	-568
2016	3,191	3,211	4,159	-20	-968
2017	5,786	6,065	5,959	-279	-173
2018	8,124	8,472	7,644	-348	+480
2019	5,628	4,600	6,502	+1,082	-974

Source: Own calculations based on the data from NIS, 2020 [8].

Making a comparison between the annual maize yield achieved in Romania in the last decade, we may easily notice that Constanta County carried out lower yields, the unfavorable years being, in the decreasing order of yield differences: 2013, 2014, 2016, 2019, 2015 and 2017, which show that Constanta County was very much affected by climate factors compared to other areas of the country, which resulted in a diminished productivity, lower farmers' income and a reduced

contribution of Constanta agriculture to the agriculture of Dobrogea region. The yield losses ranged between -1,215 kg/ha in the year 2013 and -173 kg/ha in the year 2017 (Table 4).

3.4. Differences regarding sunflower and rape yields versus Romania's yield

Comparing sunflower yield in Constanta County with Romania's yield for this crop, we may notice that in almost all the years of the decade 2010-2019, yields in this county were much lower, except the year 2017 and 2018, when Constanta County achieved higher production levels (Table 5).

Table 5. Differences in sunflower seeds and rape yields in Constanta County compared to the yield in Romania, 2010-2019 (kg/ha)

	Sunflower yield (kg/ha)			Rape yield (kg/ha)		
	Constanta County	Romania	Differences versus Romania	Constanta County	Romania	Differences versus Romania
2010	1,538	1,797	-59	1,875	1,755	+120
2011	1,343	1,798	-455	1,342	1,882	-540
2012	1,126	1,310	-184	1,690	1,496	+194
2013	1,495	1,993	-498	1,720	2,408	-688
2014	1,834	2,187	-353	2,167	2,604	-437
2015	1,597	1,765	-168	2,301	2,499	-198
2016	1,502	1,955	-453	2,293	2,835	-542
2017	3,180	2,917	+263	2,211	2,798	-587
2018	3,715	3,041	+674	2,288	2,546	-258
2019	2,660	2,783	-123	2,126	2,254	-138

Source: Own calculations based on the data from NIS, 2020 [8].

Taking into account the negative variation of yield, the unfavorable years for sunflower crop in Constanta County, in the decreasing order, were: 2013, 2011, 2016, 2014, 2012, 2015, 2019 and 2010, when yield losses varied between -498 kg/ha in 2013 and -59 kg/ha in 2010.

In case of rape, the seeds yield was lower than the national yield in the years: 2013, 2017, 2016, 2011, 2014, 2018, 2015, 2019, the losses ranging between -138 kg/ha in 2011 and - 688 kg/ha in 2019 (Table 5).

Conclusions

(1) Agriculture of Constanta County is extremely important for Romania as it brings a substantial contribution to Romania's agricultural output in general, and especially to cereal and oilseeds production.

(2) Unfortunately, climate change with which Constanta County is facing: high temperatures, decline in the amount of precipitations, pedological drought have affected during the last decade cultivated surface and mainly production performance per hectare, which have led to substantial production losses, the decrease of the farmers' income, the increase of the risk for not covering production costs and going to fail.

(3) In the analyzed decade, 2010-2019, Constanta County obtained good wheat and barley production per ha, higher than the average yield in Dobrogea region and in Romania.

(4) In case of maize, Constanta County registered a lower productivity both compared to the average production per surface unit in Dobrogea region and at the national level.

(5) Also, in case of sunflower and rape crops, Constanta County achieved lower yields in comparison with the decade average in Dobrogea region.

(6) It is worth to mention that farmers have paid a high attention to the weather forecast warnings, and they took important measures and found alternatives for adapting production technologies for each crop to diminish the impact of climate change factors, and especially to drought. In this respect, they tried to use varieties and hybrids of high production potential and resistant to drought, diseases and pests, they changed the sowing moment and the sowing depth in relationship with the soil temperature and moisture, and applied a suitable fertilization and plant protection.

(7) The year 2019 was characterized by a very strong drought which has continued in the year 2020. The insufficient amount of precipitations, the high temperatures over 32°C for a long period of time, and coupled with the lack of irrigation systems in Constanta County have led to lower yields.

(8) Many farmers were in the situation not to be able to cover production cost by the obtained yields, many of them being in danger to fail, because they had to pay the suppliers of agricultural inputs, to reimburse money to banks and leasing companies, to pay the rent to lessors.

(9) To fight against drought and to avoid production losses and the transformation of Constanta County and Dobrogea region into an arid area and desert, the following recommendations are suggested:

- farmers to continue to adapt production technologies to climate change, using cultivars and hibrids highly resistant to drought, diseases and pests, choosing a sowing period adapted to the temperature and water reserve into the soil, a corresponding fertilization and plant protection to achieve the desired yields;
- forest curtains against drought, desertification and for crop protect are compulsory to be created;
- irrigation systems for supplying water from the Danube - Black Sea Channel are compulsory to be installed;
- investments from the public budget are required for assuring water supply through the main channels and pumping stations;
- farmers have to rebuilt the secondary installations which have to allow them the access to irrigation water source;
- the aids offered by Government to support farmers who registered damages and losses due to pedological drought like in the year 2020 have to be set up according to production and not according to the cultivated area.

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STUDY ON THE AGROFORESTRY SYSTEM WITH OAK TREES (*Quercus robur* L.) IN THE CONTEXT OF CHANGING CLIMATE

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Abstract. *The permanent meadows from the plains and hills of Transylvania, grazed with cattle from ancient times, are covered with scattered trees providing shade to animals. The current global warming underline the need for the protection of animals and the vegetal layer of the meadows from the sunlight and drought. In this paper, we studied the positive effects of the presence of trees on the productivity and biodiversity of meadows in comparison with the treeless surfaces exposed to a more accentuated aridity. Under oak trees (*Quercus robur* L.) we found 57 plant species compared to 45 in open land, with over 13 t/ha green mass production compared to approx. 10 t/ha in open land and a pastoral value of approximately 69 compared to 56 of a treeless grassland. In addition to increasing biodiversity and productivity, under the oak trees the agrochemical values of the soil increase, having also additional production of acorns, animal shade and pastoral landscapes.*

Keywords: grassland with oak trees, biodiversity, grass production, pastoral value

1. Introduction

According to WMO (World Meteorological Organization) data, in the century (1901-2000) the average temperature of the globe increased by 0.6 Celsius degrees. For Romania this increase is only 0.3⁰C.

One of the most effective measures to fight against climate changes is to expand the agroforestry system already in use in the countries with drier climates.

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This system is known as 'dehesa' and 'montando' in Spain and Portugal as well as “agroforestry” in the USA [8, 9].

Due to the ecological conditions from our country in some areas there are in use several combinations of agriculture and woody vegetation such as: pasture - trees (grove, glade, hurst), hayfields - fruit trees (orchards), arable crops - fruit trees and other mixed forms [3, 4, 5].

The accentuation of global warming in the last decade, which also affects our country, has raised the issue of studying the existing agroforestry systems in order to promote them in the future. There are already numerous studies in this direction at European and global level [1, 2].

In Romania, these researches are at the beginning, in this paper being presented a case study for the combination of grassland - oak trees from South Eastern Transylvania.

2. Materials and methods

The studies on the agroforestry system pasture – oak trees were carried out in the village of Mercheașa belonging to the commune of Homorod, located in the plateau with the same name from South Eastern Transylvania (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Agroforestry system pasture – oak trees, Mercheașa Village, Homorod Plateau, South Eastern Transylvania, Romania

2. Materials and methods

The studies on the agroforestry system pasture – oak trees were carried out in the village of Mercheaşa belonging to the commune of Homorod, located in the plateau with the same name from South Eastern Transylvania (Figure 1).

Here, on an area of 40 hectares we found 85 trees of the species *Quercus robur* L., most of them being century-old. Among them a specimen with a height of 21 m and a stem diameter of almost 3 m was evaluated as being over 900 years old, considered the oldest in our country.

Specifically, floristic surveys were carried out under the canopy of oaks and in parallel in open ground. Soil samples were taken at a depth of 0-10 cm and also plant samples were collected for agrochemical and feed quality determinations, according to usual methods.

Based on the floristic surveys, the productivity of the vegetal layer (pastoral value and fodder production) was evaluated according to a new method [7].

2. Results and discussions

The following table shows the results of soil agrochemical analyses that have a direct influence on grass productivity (Table 1).

Table 1. Agrochemical values of soil samples collected from open ground and from under the oaks (*Quercus robur*)

Specification	unit	1.Open ground	2. Under the oaks	Diff. 2-1 +, -	%
pH in H ₂ O	ind.	5.2	5.35	+0.05	103
Humus	%	7.01	7.19	+0.18	103
Nitrogen index	%	4.64	4.99	+0.25	108
Mobile phosphorus	ppm	2.7	10.0	+7.3	370
Mobile potassium	ppm	168	> 400	> 232	> 238
Amount of exchangeable bases	me/100g	16.7	19.4	+2.7	116
Hydrolytic acidity	me/100g	8.5	8.5	0	100
Cation exchange capacity CEC	me/100g	25.2	27.9	+2.7	111
Base saturation BS	%	66.3	69.5	+3.2	105
Exchangeable aluminum	me/100g	0.099	0.075	-0.024	76

From these data it results that all agrochemical parameters are more favorable under oaks compared to the open field soil, without shade.

Thus, the reaction of the soil (pH) the degree of saturation in bases (BS%) and humus (%) are higher by 3-5% and the exchangeable aluminium lower by 24%. Fertilizers (P, K) are 2-4 times higher under trees than in open ground, mainly due to the manure of animals that are resting in their shade.

The improvement of soil properties changed for the better the composition and productivity of the grass carp (Table 2).

Table 2. Floristic composition of open ground (L) and from under oak trees (U) from grassland of Mercheașa – Homorod, 530 m of altitude

Species	Presence (class)		Participation %			%	Index	
	L	U	L	U	Diff.+ -		F	M
Vegetation layer	x	x	97.0	97.7	+0.7	101	x	x
Poaceae								
<i>Festuca rupicola</i>	V	V	29.4	28.0	-1.4	95	5	5
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	V	IV	10.5	6.3	-4.2	60	7	5
<i>Lolium perene</i>	IV	V	2.3	23.4	+21.1	1,017	9	8
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	IV	II	1.6	1.6	+0.0	100	7	4
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	III	II	2.8	0.4	-2.4	14	3	0
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	II	I	0.8	0.2	-0.6	25	3	0
<i>Briza media</i>	II	-	0.3	-	x	x	5	2
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	I	I	0.5	0.5	+0.0	100	5	3
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	I	I	0.2	0.2	+0.0	100	8	9
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	I	I	0.2	0.2	+0.0	100	3	0
<i>Festuca arundinaceae</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	8	9
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	-	II	-	0.3	x	x	9	8
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	6	6
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	-	I	-	0.3	x	x	9	8
<i>Poa annua</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	7	2
<i>Bromus secalinus</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
Fabaceae								
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	V	V	11.6	7.6	-4.0	66	8	5
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	V	V	3.2	3.3	+0.1	103	8	7
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	V	III	4.3	0.8	-3.5	19	8	6
<i>Genista tinctoria</i>	III	II	2.4	0.5	-1.9	21	3	0
<i>Dorycnium pentaphyllum</i>	I	-	0.5	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Medicago falcata</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	7	6
Other plant families								
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	V	V	2.6	2.3	-0.3	88	6	1
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	V	IV	2.1	1.3	-0.8	62	6	4
<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	IV	V	1.1	1.8	+0.7	164	5	3
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	IV	III	3.8	1.6	-2.2	42	4	2
<i>Pyrus piraster</i>	IV	III	1.5	0.5	-1.0	33	3	0
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	IV	II	1.0	0.4	-0.6	40	3	0

<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	III	V	1.1	5.3	+4.2	482	7	3
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	III	III	0.9	0.5	-0.4	56	3	0
<i>Centaureum erythrea</i>	III	I	0.5	0.1	-0.4	20	3	0
<i>Fragaria viridis</i>	II	IV	1.0	1.0	+0.0	100	4	1
<i>Daucus carota</i>	II	III	0.5	0.7	+0.2	140	6	5
<i>Filipendula hexapetala</i>	II	I	1.0	0.3	-0.7	30	5	4
<i>Galium verum</i>	II	I	0.8	0.2	-0.6	25	5	4
<i>Ranunculus acer</i>	II	I	0.5	0.2	-0.3	40	1	0
<i>Salvia pratensis</i>	II	I	0.9	0.1	-0.8	11	4	4
<i>Thymus montanum</i>	II	I	0.9	0.1	-0.8	11	4	2
<i>Plantago major</i>	I	IV	0.2	1.5	+1.3	750	5	3
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	I	II	0.1	0.3	+0.2	300	5	6
<i>Rosa canina</i>	I	II	0.1	0.3	+0.2	300	3	0
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	I	I	0.3	0.1	-0.2	33	3	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	I	I	0.4	0.1	-0.3	25	3	0
<i>Ranunculus sardous</i>	I	I	0.1	0.2	+0.1	200	1	0
<i>Carex palescens</i>	IV	-	2.2	-	x	x	4	3
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	III	-	1.2	-	x	x	4	6
<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	II	-	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Carduus achantoides</i>	I	-	0.2	-	x	x	2	0
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	I	-	0.2	-	x	x	2	0
<i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i>	I	-	0.2	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i>	I	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	-	V	-	1.7	x	x	5	3
<i>Geranium pratense</i>	-	II	-	0.3	x	x	4	4
<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	-	II	-	0.4	x	x	3	0
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	6	4
<i>Capsella bursa pastoris</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	4	3
<i>Galium cruciata</i>	-	I	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Lamium maculatum</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	4	6
<i>Myosotis arvensis</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Quercus robur (puieți)</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Rhinanthus glaber</i>	-	I	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Sisymbrium officinale</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	4	2
<i>Viola arvensis</i>	-	I	-	0.2	x	x	3	0

Total species (nr.)	45	57	+12	126	x	x
From which: - fodder	26	33	+7	127	x	x
- not fodder	19	24	+5	126	x	x
Participation of fodder species	83.5	91.8	+8.3	110	x	x
Participation of harmful species	13.5	5.9	-7.6	44	x	x
Bare soil	3.0	2.3	-0.7	78	x	x
Pastoral value (PV)	56.3	68.8	+12.5	122	x	x
Phytomass index	3.92	4.95	+1.03	126	x	x
Fodder production (GM t/ha)	9.79	13.36	+3.57	136	x	x

It is observed that the species *Lolium perenne*, very good fodder species, with an average participation of 2.3% in open ground is over 10 times better represented under oaks.

In general, the number of forage species increases under trees by 28% and overall participation in phytomass by 10% influencing the productivity of the vegetal layer which is more valuable under trees.

Specifically, the estimated pastoral value (PV) increases from 56.6 to 70.7 respectively by 25% and feed production (GM t/ha) from 9.6 to 14.2 t/ha, an increase of 48%, which confirms the economic value of the vegetal layer under the oaks.

The better quality of the feed under oaks was also confirmed by chemical analysis (Table 3).

Table 3. The differences between the chemical quality parameters of the grass, from open ground (L) and under trees (U) from Mercheașa

Chemical parameters for feed quality	Participation %			%
	L	U	Diff. + -	
CP	17.1	19.7	+2.6	115
ASH	10.5	11.3	+0.8	107
FB	28.5	27.3	-1.2	96
ADF	32.6	31.4	-1.3	96
ADL	3.7	2.7	-1.1	71
NDF	53.5	52.8	-0.7	99
DMD	63.4	69.4	+6.0	110
OMD	58.6	65.9	+7.3	113

Thus, the crude protein content (CP) and the digestibility of the dry matter (DMD) or of the organic matter (OMD) are 10-15% higher for the grass under the trees than for the grass from the grassland's open field.

The data show that the optimal digestibility of feed (important indicator of conversion into animal products) of over 65% is found only under trees (65.9 - 69.4%).

To all these advantages of the agroforestry system with oaks we can add the production and feed quality of the acorn, the shade for the welfare of the animals and the protection of the vegetal layer during the hot periods. So, the next stage of research will have to establish the quantity and quality of acorns produced by these oaks, as well as the welfare of animals that benefit from shade, parameters that are more difficult to quantify.

Conclusions

(1) The agrochemical properties of the soil under oaks (*Quercus robur*) are much more favorable for plant growth than open ground conditions.

(2) Grass production and fodder quality is better under oaks than in grasslands located in open field by 25-50%.

(3) In the conditions of global climate warming the agroforestry system with oaks, due to its economic, protective and aesthetic qualities, needs to be preserved and expanded.

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THE NEED FOR THE CONSERVATION AND EXTENSION OF THE AGROSILVOPASTORAL SYSTEM WITH DOWNY OAK (*QUERCUS PUBESCENS* Willd.) IN DOBROGEA, ROMANIA

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Abstract. *On fairly large areas of the Dobrogean Plateau we can find agroforestry systems, respectively dry grasslands with isolated trees of downy oak or other tree species (e.g. *Carpinus orientalis*, *Quercus pedunculiflora*), which provides shade for animals. Our study shows a higher level of nutrients in the soil under the oaks, due to organic fertilizers resulting from animals sheltering in the shade. Also, in the vegetal layer under the oaks, the participation of forage species represents 56%, by 20% higher than in the treeless grassland. Therefore, the pastoral value of the grassland under the oaks reaches 37 points, almost 16 points higher than in the open field. Also, the fodder production exceeds 4t / ha of green mass, more than double that of the grassland located outside the shade of the trees. To these advantages regarding the productivity of the grasslands from the agrosilvopastoral system we can add the acorn production of the oaks and the beneficial effect of the shade for the animals. All these results argue for the conservation and expansion of the agroforestry system in the context of global warming.*

Keywords: agrosilvopastoral system, dry grasslands, pastoral value, feed production

1. Introduction

Global warming has accelerated research on agroforestry or agrosilvopastoral systems as a measure to prevent the effects of high temperatures and lack of rainfall [1,8,9].

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In our country the agrosilvopastoral systems are more extensive in Dobrogea, as a result of the deforestation of the oak forests concessioned by the English from the Ottoman Empire, from the middle of the 19th century [10].

During that period, given the arid climate, some of the downy oaks were left on the meadows to provide shade for the animals.

Although it is an effective method of counteracting the effects of global warming [3,6], at national level there are few studies and research on the interaction between grasslands and scattered trees, a combination assimilated with the agroforestry system [4, 5].

Thus, the increasing warming of the climate in areas with higher aridity such as Dobrogea, raised the issue of initiating and deepening the research on existing agrosilvopastoral systems and their improvement and expansion.

2. Materials and methods

The studies were carried out on the grasslands with downy oaks from the commune of Cerna, the village of General Praporgescu, located at the confluence of the North Dobrogean Plateau with the Măcin Mountains.

We analyzed 14 plots, of which 7 areas with well-developed downy oaks, for each of them being evaluated a control area located in a permanent grassland without trees from the immediate vicinity.

Floristic surveys were carried out under the canopy of oaks and in open land on 100 sq m each, the participation of the species in the composition of the vegetal layer being appreciated directly in percentages.

For the plots located under oaks, 4 soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-10 cm from half the distance between the edge of the canopy and the trunk of the trees, as well as from the edge of the canopy, on a circular sample surface. For the plots in the grasslands without trees, 4 soil samples were also collected on the diagonals of the sample surface (10 x 10 m). Soil samples were collected using a soil corer with an inside diameter of 25 mm. The sampled material was analyzed in the laboratory according to the usual methodology for soil agrochemical analyzes [2].

Due to the excessive drought and the overgrazing in August, it was not possible to take fodder samples.

The pastoral value and the production of green mass of fodder were evaluated based on floristic surveys carried out under downy oaks and in open field grasslands, according to the new method proposed by Marușca in 2019 [6].

3. Results and discussions

The soil analysis showed that under the trees the content of fertilizers is higher than on the dry grasslands located in open field. (Table 1).

Table 1. Main agrochemical and physical values of grassland soil from open field and under trees

Specification	UM	1. Open land	2. Under canopy	Dif. 2-1 +, -	%
pH in H ₂ O	ind.	7.20	6.85	-0.35	95
Base saturation BS	%	100.0	96.3	-3.8	96
Humus	%	7.07	7.42	+0.35	105
Nitrogen index	%	7.07	7.14	+0.07	101
Mobile phosphorus (P)	ppm	31.0	54.0	+23.0	174
Mobile potassium (K)	ppm	>400	>400	0	100
Carbonates	%	2.85	-	x	x
Rocks with a diameter <25 mm	%	13.1	4.4	-8.7	34
Roots on 0-10 cm depth	%	1.2	1.9	+0.7	158

From these data it results that under the trees the soil reaction has a slight decrease, the humus content and the nitrogen index increase by 1-5% and that of mobile phosphorus by 74% on a very well supplied background in potassium.

Among the physical components, under trees the rock content below 25 mm is one third lower than on open field grasslands, probably due to the protection offered by the canopy to the soil layer against erosion factors.

Compared to the vegetal layer in uncovered land, the more favorable content in fertilizer elements under the trees improved the floristic composition with good forage species. (Table 2).

Table 2. Floristic composition and productivity of grasslands in open field (L) and under downy oaks (U) in Cerna commune, Tulcea county, 260 m of altitude

Species	Presence (class)		Participation %			%	Index	
	L	U	L	U	Dif.+ -		F*	M**
Vegetation cover	x	x	86.4	68.7	-17.7	80	x	x
Poaceae								
<i>Botrichloa ischaemum</i>	V	III	37.4	1.3	-36.1	3	3	0
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	III	V	20.1	21.1	+1.0	105	6	2
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	III	V	6.7	18.3	+11.6	272	5	3
<i>Stipa capillata</i>	II	IV	1.0	1.1	+0.1	114	3	0
<i>Eragrostis minor</i>	I	II	0.1	0.6	+0.4	400	3	0
<i>Chrysopogon gryllus</i>	I	-	4.3	-	x	x	4	7
<i>Bombicilena erecta</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	6	6

<i>Lolium perenne</i>	-	III	-	7.3	x	x	9	8
<i>Brachypodium sylvaticum</i>	-	II	-	3.7	x	x	5	7
<i>Dactylis polygama</i>	-	II	-	0.3	x	x	7	7
<i>Melica ciliata</i>	-	I	-	0.3	x	x	4	2
<i>Koeleria lobata</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	5	3
<i>Hordeum hystrix</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	5	3
Fabaceae								
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	8	6
Other plant families								
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	III	IV	3.1	1.1	-2.0	36	3	0
<i>Artemisia austriaca</i>	III	IV	1.7	1.1	-0.6	67	2	0
<i>Potentilla argentea</i>	III	IV	0.7	0.9	+0.1	120	4	2
<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i>	III	III	0.9	0.4	-0.4	50	3	0
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	III	II	0.9	1.1	+0.3	133	5	1
<i>Teucrium polium</i>	III	I	1.1	0.1	-1.0	13	3	0
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	II	V	0.6	2.3	1.7	400	3	0
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	II	IV	0.4	1.1	0.7	267	6	4
<i>Centaurea diffusa</i>	II	II	0.3	0.3	0.0	100	2	0
<i>Carthamus lanatus</i>	II	I	0.4	0.1	-0.3	33	3	0
<i>Marrubium peregrinum</i>	II	I	0.4	0.7	+0.3	167	3	0
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	I	III	0.1	0.4	0.3	300	6	1
<i>Asperula cynanchica</i>	I	II	0.1	0.6	0.4	400	3	0
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	I	II	0.1	0.3	0.1	200	5	6
<i>Scleranthus annuus</i>	I	I	0.1	0.1	0.0	100	3	0
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	IV	-	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	III	-	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Taraxacum serotinum</i>	II	-	0.6	-	x	x	5	2
<i>Thymus pannonicus</i>	II	-	0.6	-	x	x	4	2
<i>Thymus zygioides</i>	II	-	0.6	-	x	x	4	1
<i>Carduus kernerii</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	2	0
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	5	6
<i>Convolvulus cantabricus</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Helichrisum arenarium</i>	I	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Orlaya grandiflora</i>	I	-	0.7	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Rosa canina</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Salsola kali ruthenica</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Satureja coerulea</i>	I	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Torillis arvensis</i>	I	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Verbascum phoeniceum</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	-	II	-	0.6	x	x	3	0
<i>Carpinus orientalis (juv)</i>	-	II	-	1.7	x	x	3	0
<i>Achillea pannonica</i>	-	I	-	0.4	x	x	6	5
<i>Alyssum alyssoides</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Heliotropium europeus</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	5	3
<i>Galium verum</i>	-	I	-	0.3	x	x	5	4

Total species(nr.)	38	34	-4	89	x	x
From wich: - fodder	14	16	+2	114	x	x
- not fodder	24	18	-6	75	x	x
Participation of fodder species	35.6	56.0	+20.4	157	x	x
Participation of harmful species	50.8	12.7	-38.1	25	x	x
Bare soil	13.6	31.3	+17.7	230	x	x
Pastoral value (PV)	21.4	36.9	+15.5	172	x	x
Phytomass index	1.00	1.98	+0.98	198	x	x
Fodder production (GM t/ha)	1.91	4.16	+2.25	218	x	x

*) F – Feed value index

**) M – Useful green mass index

From these data it results that the main non-valuable forage species *Botriochloa ischaemum* which appears in open field in proportion of over 37% decreases under oaks to almost 1%. Instead of this weed, in the shade of oaks, the proportion of forage species such as *Festuca valesiaca* increases by 12% and *Lolium perenne* by 7%, species that have a decisive role in increasing the productivity of these steppe grasslands.

Under the trees, where the animals rest in the shade and the insolation is lower, the forage species participate in proportion of 56% in the composition of vegetal layer, with 20% more than in open field.

Thus, the pastoral value under trees reaches 37 points compared to 21 in the open field and the production of green mass of fodder exceeds 4 t/ha under oaks, more than double what was evaluated on the open field grasslands.

All these data confirm the superiority of the vegetal layer under the downy oaks compared to that of the open field grasslands. In addition, the production of acorns can be valued as feed for sheep and goats, the animals that benefit from the shade produce from 20 to 40% more milk and meat and the pastoral landscape with trees is more attractive.

Conclusions

- (1) The agroforestry system with downy oak is superior in all aspects: productive, protective and aesthetic compared to the steppe grasslands without trees.
- (2) The conservation of the current agroforestry systems and the extension of the trees on the permanent dry grasslands are measures that can prevent aridization and desertification in an already affected area, such as Dobrogea.

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STUDIES REGARDING THE EVOLUTION OF GRASSLAND PRODUCTIVITY FROM CODRU MOMA MOUNTAINS (WESTERN CARPATHIANS)

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Abstract. Knowledge of the dynamics of floristic composition and the productivity of permanent grasslands has a special scientific and practical value. This work presents a comparative study of grassland vegetation in 1937 and in 2011 in terms of floristics and productivity for 4 phytocoenoses spread in the Codru Moma Mountains in the northern part of Western Carpathians (Apuseni Mountains). After almost three quarters of a century, *Festuceto rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* and *Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris* associations located near the localities used for grazing as communal pastures or hayfields, have generally preserved their biodiversity, increased their pastoral value by 8-23% and the fodder green mass production by 21-22%. Instead *Poterio-Festucetum valesiaca* association located on steep slopes and sunny exhibitions together with the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association, both located at greater distances from localities, during the same period, decreased their pastoral value by 13-39% and fodder green mass production by 17-35%. At a more detailed analysis of the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association, it was found that the invasive *Nardus stricta* species from an average participation of 45.6% in 1937 reached 66.9% in 2011, respectively by more than 20%, indicating the stage of continuous degradation of the herbaceous layer and decreasing productivity.

Keywords: grassland vegetation, productivity dynamics, carrying capacity

1. Introduction

The study of the herbaceous layer of the grasslands has a special importance both for phytocenological classification and for establishing improvement measures and rational use included in pastoral arrangements.

New evaluation methods of grassland phytocoenosis productivity based on floristic surveys made it possible to establish the evolution in dynamics of this very important indicator for the pastoral economy [3].

Till now there have been few studies on grassland productivity dynamics of which we mention the one made on the steppe grasslands after 45-50 years from the Babadag and Casimcea plateaus from Dobrogea [4].

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In this paper we performed a comparative study of grassland productivity after almost 75 years, in Codru-Moma Mountains (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Geographical location of Codru Moma Mountains [10] (modified)

2. Materials and methods

For studying grassland productivity dynamics from Codru Moma Mountains, the following synthesis works were examined: ”*Photosociological studies in the Codru Moma Mountains*” made by Ana Paucă [5], ”*Flora and vegetation of the Codru Moma Mountains*”, doctoral thesis prepared by Pășcuț C.G. [8], and some more recent works [6, 7].

Floristic surveys for the description of vegetation were drawn up according to the methodology of the floristic school of Zurich-Montpellier or Braun-Blanquet in the summers of 1937 and 2011, during a period of almost 75 years [2]. For the determination of the species in the field we used specialised works developed by Ciocârlan and Sârbu et al. [1, 9].

In order to be compared, we studied only the associations of the same stationary conditions, which overlap (Table 1).

At the evaluation of grassland productivity the method based on floristic surveys was used [3, 4].

These results which can be compared in dynamics, after a longer period of time, allow us to know the direction of evolution of grassland productivity considering their management.

Table 1. Stationary conditions of the grasslands associations from the Codru Moma Mountains (Western Carpathians)

No.	Association	Altitude (m.s.m)	Exposition	Slope (degrees)	Location
1	<i>Poterio-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	490-510	V, SV	14-40	Rasteț Hill
2	<i>Anthoxantho-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	290-350	Plane - N	0-6	Gropi Hill
3	<i>Festuceto rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris</i>	640-700	E,V,SV,N	4-18	Bănișoara Sfârș
4	<i>Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax</i>	640-800	Plane, S,V,N,NE	0-25	Ponoare Glade, Brătcoia Glade, Rontaru Hill

3. Results and discussions

Calculations on the evolution of grassland productivity were performed for all four more widespread associations, of which we show you the most representative with the most surveys presented in both mentioned syntheses (Table 2).

Table 2. Evolution of the floristic composition of the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association from Codru Moma Mountains, Bihor county

Species	Attendance (class)		Participation (%)			%	Indices	
	1937	2011	1937	2011	Diff. +/-		F	M
<i>Vegetation cover</i>	x	x	99.8	94.2	-5.6	94	x	x
<i>Poaceae</i>								
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	V	V	45.6	66.9	+21.3	147	3	0
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	V	V	2.6	6.6	+4.0	254	7	6
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	V	V	0.5	0.5	0	100	4	3
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	V	IV	12.8	2.2	-10.6	17	4	3
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	V	IV	2.6	0.4	-2.2	15	7	5
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	V	II	4.4	0.2	-4.2	5	5	3
<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i>	V	I	0.5	0.1	-0.4	20	3	0
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	IV	II	0.4	0.2	-0.2	50	6	6

<i>Briza media</i>	III	II	0.3	0.2	-0.1	67	5	2
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	III	II	0.3	0.2	-0.1	67	3	0
<i>Molinia coerulea</i>	V	-	8.2	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	7	4
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	9	8
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	9	8
<i>Calamagrostis epigeios</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Agrostis gigantea</i>	-	IV	-	1.3	x	x	7	7
<i>Fabaceae</i>								
<i>Gemistella sagittalis</i>	IV	III	0.4	2.1	+0.7	525	3	0
<i>Cytisus nigricans</i>	IV	I	0.4	0.1	-0.3	25	3	0
<i>Genista tinctoria</i>	IV	-	0.4	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	8	7
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	8	5
<i>Trifolium medium</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	6	4
<i>Vicia tetrasperma</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	6	3
<i>Others Families</i>								
<i>Luzula campestris</i>	V	V	0.5	0.5	0	100	4	2
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	V	IV	1.5	1.3	-0.2	87	5	2
<i>Succisa pratensis</i>	V	III	1.5	0.3	-1.2	20	3	0
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	V	III	1.5	1.2	-0.3	80	3	0
<i>Stachys officinalis</i>	V	II	0.5	0.2	-0.3	40	3	0
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	V	I	0.5	0.1	-0.4	20	4	1
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	IV	III	0.4	0.3	-0.1	75	4	1
<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	IV	III	0.4	0.3	-0.1	75	4	5
<i>Veratrum album</i>	IV	III	0.4	0.3	-0.1	75	1	0
<i>Carex pallescens</i>	IV	II	0.4	0.2	-0.2	50	4	3
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	IV	II	0.4	0.2	-0.2	50	5	5
<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	IV	II	0.4	0.2	-0.2	50	3	0
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	IV	II	1.5	3.6	+2.1	240	3	0
<i>Dianthus carthusianorum</i>	IV	I	0.4	0.1	-0.3	25	3	0
<i>Cytisus nigricans</i>	IV	I	0.4	0.1	-0.3	25	3	0
<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	IV	I	0.4	0.2	-0.2	50	3	0
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	III	IV	0.3	0.4	-0.1	133	4	4
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	III	III	0.3	0.3	0	100	6	4
<i>Campanula patula</i>	III	II	0.3	0.2	-0.1	67	3	0
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	III	II	0.3	0.2	-0.1	67	4	6
<i>Galium verum</i>	III	I	0.3	0.1	-0.2	33	5	4
<i>Lychnis viscaria</i>	III	I	0.3	0.1	-0.2	33	4	4

<i>Antennaria dioica</i>	III	I	0.3	0.1	-0.2	33	4	2
<i>Galium mollugo</i>	I	III	0.1	0.3	+0.2	300	3	0
<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	I	III	0.1	0.3	+0.2	300	4	2
<i>Ajuga genevensis</i>	I	I	0.1	0.1	0	100	4	2
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	I	I	0.1	0.1	0	100	6	1
<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Gymnadenia conopsea</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	2	0
<i>Hypericum tetrapterum</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	2	0
<i>Rhinanthus minor</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Viola tricolor</i>	III	-	0.3	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>	III	-	0.1	-	x	x	5	3
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	4	2
<i>Prunella laciniata</i>	I	-	0.1	-	x	x	4	2
Other species 1937 (K 1; P 0.1%; F 1.2.3.): <i>Antherus arvensis</i> , <i>Campanula glomerata</i> , <i>Campanula persicifolia</i> , <i>Carex flava</i> , <i>Carex ovata</i> , <i>Carlina acaulis</i> , <i>Cerastium holosteoides</i> , <i>Crepis paludosa</i> , <i>Dactylorhiza maculata</i> , <i>Dactylorhiza sambucina</i> , <i>Gentianella lutescens</i> , <i>Gladiolus imbricantus</i> , <i>Hypochaeris</i> <i>maculata</i> , <i>Lysimachia punctata</i> , <i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i> , <i>Prunus spinosa</i> , <i>Pteridium</i> <i>aquilinum</i> , <i>Solidago virgaurea</i> .								
<i>Hypericum maculatum</i>	-	IV	-	-0.4	x	x	3	3
<i>Seseli osseum</i>	-	III	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Viola canina</i>	-	III	-	1.2	x	x	4	1
<i>Carex montana</i>	-	II	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	-	II	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i>	-	II	-	0.2	x	x	4	7
<i>Thymus dacicus</i>	-	II	-	0.2	x	x	4	2
<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	5	3
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i>	-	I	-	0.1	x	x	4	2
Other species 2011(K 1; P 0.1%; F 3.): <i>Betula pendula</i> , <i>Dianthus armeria</i> , <i>Hieracium umbellatum</i> , <i>Juniperus communis</i> , <i>Senecio</i> <i>jacobea</i> , <i>Veronica teucrium</i> .								

where: F - Fodder quality indices; M - Production indices.

These data show that for the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association, between the two studies carried out in 1937 and in 2011, there were quite big changes in the grassy layer of these permanent grasslands of secondary origin, after the deforestation that preceded them.

Thus *Nardus stricta*, the dominant species, increased in participation from 45.6% to 66.9%, that is more than 20%, *Festuca rubra* increased by 4%, *Deschampsia*

flexuosa decreased by more than 10%, *Molinia caerulea* disappeared and other minor changes occurred.

Instead, *Juniperus communis* shrubs have appeared more recently, as well as *Betula pendula* seedlings, as a result of an underload of these grasslands, used for grazing.

As far as the number of plant species is concerned, respectively phytodiversity, in 1937 this association registered 81 species and in 2011 only 57, respectively only 70% of what it was 75 years ago.

Changes in the dynamics of floristic composition had a strong influence on the dynamics of productivity in the phytocoenoses of these grasslands (Table 3).

Table 3. Productivity dynamics and grazing capacity for some grassland phytocoenoses from Codru Moma Mountains

Specification	Year	Grassland association				Average
		1. Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris	2. Poterio-Festucetum valesiacae	3. Festuco-rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris	4. Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax	
Pastoral value (PV)	1937	47.9	51.9	63.2	17.3	45.1
	2011	58.9	44.9	68.4	10.6	45.7
	Diff.+ -	+ 11.0	- 7.0	+ 5.2	- 6.7	+ 0.7
	%	123	87	108	61	101
Green mass production (GM t/ha)	1937	7.22	6.49	10.79	2.22	6.68
	2011	8,83	5,37	13.10	1.44	7.18
	Diff.+ -	+ 1.61	- 1.12	+ 2.31	- 0.78	+ 0.50
	%	122	83	121	65	107
Duration of the optimal grazing season (days)		190	175	160	160	170
Livestock units (LU/ha)	1937	0,58	0.57	1.04	0.21	0.60
	2011	0.71	0.47	1.26	0.14	0.65
	Diff.+ -	+ 0,13	- 0.10	+ 0.22	- 0.07	+ 0.05
	%	122	82	121	67	108

Thus, the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association has a pastoral value of about 7 lower indices and a green mass production of only 65% in 2011 compared to 1937.

Poterio-Festucetum valesiacae association located on the sunny slopes also records a decrease in pastoral value by 7 and a production of 83% in 2011, compared to 1937.

The other two plant associations *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* and *Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris* located near localities and better managed, have better pastoral value indices by 7 and green mass production by 21-22% higher in 2011.

On average, for the 4 phytocoenosis, the optimal loading of livestock units was 0.60 LU/ha in 1937 and 0.65 LU / ha in 2011, fairly constant for a production around 7 t/ha green mass production for about an average season of 170 days of grazing.

Conclusions

(1) In the grasslands vegetation of Codru Moma Mountains significant changes occurred over a period of three quarters of a century.

(2) The grasslands belonging to the *Nardo-Festucetum rubrae fallax* association, located at a greater distance from localities, were further invaded by the worthless *Nardus stricta* species by more than 20%, which decreased the pastoral value by 7 and feed production by 35%.

(3) The grasslands belonging to *Anthoxantho-Agrostetum capillaris* and *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* associations, near the localities, were better managed and as a result, the pastoral value is better and green mass production increased by 21-22% in 2011 compared to the reference year 1937.

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ROMANIA'S TERRITORY ADMINISTRATIVE RENEWAL IN CONVERGENCE WITH RESOURCE BALANCE AND AGRI-FOOD POTENTIAL

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Abstract. *It is known that the condition of regionalization and governance on several levels in European countries represent an EU major preoccupation (including by the Assembly of European Regions / AER), especially in the idea of as efficient as possible utilization of European financial funds. As there have been cumulated major imbalances of all kinds between Romanian counties on the basis of an obsolete model of territorial organization (with serious socio-economic and political implications), the study has as an aim to find an optimized and balanced solution, through a new approach based on the principles of the concept of societal bio harmonization. In this direction there is conceived the bio harmonization mechanism, that is methodologically based on the evolution of development in relation to natural resources (relief, waters, forests, land categories), to agro-food production and potential, to human and financial resources, to life quality (by purchasing power and life expectancy). There are used a series of calculation formulas that have in view to quantify the balance of proposed regions through objective indices (except for Bucharest Zone that functions based on different criteria, of singular metropolis in our country). Indices show that through harmonization (example: weighted arithmetic mean) there is reached a „bio harmonization” level of Romanian territory based on integration, efficiency and balancing, thus reducing development and life quality differences which induce a greater equity by approaching populations' chances of life from all proposed territorial structures.*

Keywords: societal bio harmonization, governance, living standard, regionalization, resources

1. Introduction

In a thematic approach based on the main observations offered by the present condition of regionalization in Europe [1], tendencies and perspectives lead to open questions concerning the future of the regions in the European landscape and, more broadly, the role of subnational authorities in shaping the continent. From here also comes the preoccupation regarding administrative compatibility in relation with *centralization - decentralization* on the axes: „national - transnational - regional (Euro regions) - continental (European)”.

The condition of regionalization and governance on several levels in European countries represents a major preoccupation of EU and directly of the Assembly of European Regions (AER), especially in the idea to use European financial funds as efficiently as possible.

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In this context, because Romania's specific premises, there may be observed a paradox, but also a series of disharmonies linked to the territorial administrative organization. These ones have serious socio-economic and political implications that need an immediate reform because Romania is even today organized after an obsolete model and with minor adjustments since over 50 years (since 1968). On one hand, it is observed that demographically our country has major problems (population in natural decline, unprecedented emigration in the last decades and other) that impose solutions, and on the other hand, consequently to the obsolete territorial administrative organization with 41 counties, with 103 municipalities, with approximately 2,862 communes, 216 towns (out of which a part being wrongly framed, and another part are in involution or are even completely abandoned [2]).

There inevitably result problems of administrative management, with strongly affected systemic effectiveness and economic efficiency (for example the exaggeratedly large number of „elected people” in policy and administration: over 40,000 local counselors, almost 1,400 department counselors and approximately 3,200 mayors, not to mention the 600 MPs). Anomalies appear, as for example Teleorman County with the same population as Timșoara has 1,115 local counselors face to Timșoara's 27, not to speak about Bucharest's only 55 counselors at about 2 million inhabitants population (!). As well as, without entering into details, we may mention the disorders in the administration of budgetary or European funds (even with crime aspects) due to administrative unreconstructed too.

Romania, comparatively to the other European countries, may be a little bit exaggeratedly appears as a poorly developed country, which imposes a remedial, so that proposals of renewal of territorial administrative organization become not only timely, but also of maximum urgency.

The study **main objective** is to shape a new organizational structure, more adequate to nowadays and perspective demands, that may also be an own proposal necessary to debates at European level too, in view of harmonizing financial fund absorption. As punctual objectives, the study tries to find solutions based on reality, where societal development may be correlated to *RESOURCE* existence), and necessary dynamics to renew Romania's territorial administrative organization may as much as possible take into account aspects of *BALANCE and FAIRNESS*.

2. Materials and Methods

We concretely propose ourselves an approach through a methodology that may quantify the balance of the proposed regions by *OBJECTIVE INDICATORS* that

may express the contribution of types of resources that sustain the perennial existence of the expected territorial organizational units, but also the citizens' life quality from the proposed territorial structures. There is used the multi-criteria analysis, MCA [11], respectively the method of *scoring and weighting* (in MVA techniques information from basic matrix is usually converted into coherent numeric values). Performance matrices preview THREE stages: (1) **Scoring**: expected consequences for every option receive a numeric score on a scale of the preference level for every option for every criterion; (2) **Weighting**: there are assigned numeric weights in order to define, for every criterion, relative estimations of oscillations between inferior limit and superior limit of the chosen scale; (3) **Indicator quantification by weighted arithmetic mean (Mw)**, [6]:

$$M_p = \frac{a_1 \cdot p_1 + a_2 \cdot p_2 + \dots + a_n \cdot p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}$$

where: **a₁, a₂, ... a_n** represent numbers,
with **p₁, p₂, ... p_n** weights.

3. Results and Discussions

In order to make a model of Romania's territorial reorganization, an as objective and balanced one, the study starts from **fixing** principles, work hypothesis and mechanisms to implement predetermined objectives. We first refer to the following **PRINCIPLES**: - The principle of multi-level and multi-criterial territorial balance / - The principle of resource diversity harmonization / - The principle of debureaucratization and optimization of the centralization-decentralization relation / - The principle of minimizing disadvantages and risks. At the same time one starts from the **hypothesis** of making an **as balanced as possible model**, that may be sustained by a comprehensive and integrative mechanism. There is described „*the bio harmonization mechanism*” based on the Bioharmonism Theory [4].

The consequences of application of these principles and mechanisms lead to a territorial reorganization based on the **balance of diversity** of aspects and as much as possible avoidance of imbalance and inequalities. It is envisaged a „radial” redivision of the territory, from central zones towards frontiers, in order to include as many forms of relief and altitude as possible, but also natural, economic, social and cultural diversity, necessary to integration and getting an as stable as possible balance in time. It is in fact avoided the present concept of division on concentric parallel areas, that, by lack of resource diversity, make territorial structures little sustainable (mono economy, social and cultural barriers) which, for years, has led to accentuating the living standard differences and too much imbalance between regions.

The new model aims at an administrative-territorial reform that also organically comprises the creation of territorial structures (for example named: regions, departments, cantons etc.) administrated by elected authorities and having clear functions (and who will be able to be also in charge of European fund management in legal and unequivocal conditions). This presupposes CONCEPTUAL RENEWAL concerning administrative reorganization of Romania's territory, the **new model** imposing to analyze the following elements on the principles of the bio harmonist ideology [5] of socio-economic, but also psychological (mental and behavior one) „release”:

- *Element 1:* Government's correct and ethical implication in applying European rules in relation with concrete conditions from Romania.
- *Element 2:* Imposing meritocracy by objective criteria and, implicitly, by the level of professional preparation concerning European fund absorption.
- *Element 3:* Sustaining financial mechanisms and specialized banks for the idea of developing territorial structures (especially in decentralization fine adjustment).
- *Element 4:* Legal rethinking of public administration by coherent legislative changes.
- *Element 5:* Digitalization and education focused on organizational culture.
- *Element 6:* Depoliticize administration and transparency of management of national and European financial funds.

3.1. Imbalances from present territorial organization

It must be mentioned that the present territorial organization of Romania is over a half century old (Fig.1), situation during which there have been cumulated major imbalances of all kinds between counties [3].

Fig.1. Present territorial administrative organization of Romania

Without entering into details, we start, as a comparison basis, with an eloquent example that indicates the present major imbalances between counties, namely the county GDP variation from the year 2019 (with a total of 763.774 thousand lei, not taking into account the GDP in Bucharest + Ilfov) (Table 1).

Table 1. Landmark of imbalances in present territorial organization (county GDP in 2019)

Counties „extreme GDP”	GDP (thousand lei)	Variation around average deviation	Extreme GDP face to GDP average
Cluj	50421	264 %	264 - 154 = + 110 %
Tulcea	8120	43 %	43 - 154 = - 110 %
GDP average on counties (without Bucharest)	763,774 thousand lei : 40 counties = 19,094.35 (average value as 100 % landmark, to which the counties with maximum and minimum GDP report)	100 %	Big variation around average deviation, between: - 110 % and + 110 %
		Difference average: $(264 + 43) / 2 =$ approx. 154 %	

From Table 1 it is observed that differences between counties are very large, in synthesis expressed through GDP. The difference deviation between counties is between **- 110 % and + 110 %**. Taking into consideration the situation in reality, differences between present counties become flagrant, so that not only financial turnover and investments are severely affected, but also the living standard, all these justifying territorial administrative reorganization.

3.2. Proposed model regarding the new territorial organization

In the current context, a rapid renewal and an optimized reorganization of the territory of the country are required, for the stated purpose to look for a geographical, ecological, demographic *bio harmonization*, with significant socio-economic impact and equal opportunities as balanced as possible in the regions of the new model. We are speaking of two groups of elements taken into consideration, respectively natural capital and human capital of the regions [9] proposed in the present model too, respectively:

- *at the natural capital*: beyond the contribution of the allocated land area and the corresponding relief, the emphasis is on the productive field „agro” and on forests, for ecologic, climate and health balance;

- *at human capital*: beyond population size, the weight increases taking into consideration the work efficiency (GDP) and the living standard (purchasing power) and finally everything being cumulated in life expectancy (longevity).

As for the **natural potential** of the considered region, there have been taken into account four criteria: surface and land quality, relief, forests and agricultural

potential, and within these criteria there are to be found six components each, with a differently fixed weight in relation to the importance for the development, all the aspects being described in synthesis in Table 2.

Table 2. Weighted criteria of the optimized model of territorial organization

TOTAL LAND		RELIEF		FORESTS		AGRO-ALIMENTARY POTENTIAL	
Area (km ²)	Points (a)	Categories	Points (a)	- Weight from the total area of the territorial unit	Points (a)	Category	Points (a)
Up to 17,500	1	Mountains	1	< 10 %	1	Total agricultural area used	2
17,500-20,000	2	Hills	1	10-20 %	2	Arable land	4
20,000-22,500	3	Plateaus	1	20-30 %	3	Family gardens	1
22,500-25,000	4	Plain	1	30-40 %	4	Pastures and meadows	3
25,000-27,500	5	Wet zones	1	40-50 %	5	Permanent cultures (ex. viticulture)	2
27,500-30,000	6	Danube Delta	1	> 50 %	6	Forest crops (nursery)	x

There have been applied the described elements, namely the established principles, there have been fixed working hypothesis and mechanisms to implement the pre-established objectives, so that there was possible to process collected primary data on this theme [7, 10, 12, 8, 13]. Variants of the resulted solutions have led to the choice of the model of administrative reorganization with 12 territorial structures, as they are described in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Variant proposed as a model of territorial administrative reorganization

In order to argue the proposal, there have been processed data on the new territories, respectively a comparison between the 11 regions, and, separately, Bucharest zone that has developed differently, after the principles of a large metropolis. Within the stages of calculation performed, there have resulted a series of intermediate tables, more eloquent being the one regarding **agro alimentary potential**.

Thus, by cumulating the surfaces of arable land, family gardens, pastures and hayfield and permanent cultures on each newly established region, there was possible to go on calculating by the weight of potential to feed the region population in comparison with the total of the region area, the obtained percentage being divided in 6 groups, as it follows:

Agro land % from the total	under 40	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-79	over 80
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6
No. Regions from the model	-	3	4	3	-	1

Concerning the **potential of human resource** in the 11 proposed regions there have been taken into consideration three criteria: density (no. inhabitants/km²), productivity (GDP region/inhabitant) and work efficiency as contribution of the given territory (GDP region/km²), and for life quality, life expectancy and purchase power. The obtained values have allowed to continue calculations by *weighting*, resulting the following 6 levels, as follows:

Population (thous. inhab.)	1.00 - 1.99	1.20 - 1.39	1.40 - 1.59	1.60 -1.79	1.80 - 1.99	Over 2.00
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

GDP (thousands lei)	under 60	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79	over 80
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Life expectancy masculine pop.	69.29-70.55	70.56-71.38	71.39-72.25	72.26-73.60	73.61-75.06
Group average	70	71	72	73	74
Life expectancy feminine pop.	77.02-77.78	77.79-78.49	78.50-79.08	79.09-79.82	79.83-80.76
Group average	77.5	78	78.5	79	80

Longevity (years)	74.50 - 74.74	74.75 - 74.99	75.00 - 75.24	75.25 - 75.49	75.50 - 75.74	Over 75
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Index purchasing power (method Gfk, 2018)	sub 75	75 - 79	80 - 84	85 - 89	90 - 94	95 and over
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Population (thous. inhab.)	1.00 - 1.99	1.20 - 1.39	1.40 - 1.59	1.60 - 1.79	1.80 - 1.99	Over 2.00
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

GDP (thousands lei)	under 60	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79	over 80
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

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Group average	70	71	72	73	74
Life expectancy feminine pop.	77.02-77.78	77.79-78.49	78.50-79.08	79.09-79.82	79.83-80.76
Group average	77.5	78	78.5	79	80

Longevity (years)	74.50 - 74.74	74.75 - 74.99	75.00 - 75.24	75.25 - 75.49	75.50 - 75.74	Over 75
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Index purchasing power (method Gfk, 2018)	sub 75	75 - 79	80 - 84	85 - 89	90 - 94	95 and over
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Population (thous. inhab.)	1.00 - 1.99	1.20 - 1.39	1.40 - 1.59	1.60 - 1.79	1.80 - 1.99	Over 2.00
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

GDP (thousands lei)	under 60	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79	over 80
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Life expectancy masculine pop.	69.29-70.55	70.56-71.38	71.39-72.25	72.26-73.60	73.61-75.06
Group average	70	71	72	73	74
Life expectancy feminine pop.	77.02-77.78	77.79-78.49	78.50-79.08	79.09-79.82	79.83-80.76
Group average	77.5	78	78.5	79	80

Longevity (years)	74.50 - 74.74	74.75 - 74.99	75.00 - 75.24	75.25 - 75.49	75.50 - 75.74	Over 75
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

Index purchasing power (method Gfk, 2018)	sub 75	75 - 79	80 - 84	85 - 89	90 - 94	95 and over
Group:	1	2	3	4	5	6

A first centralized table groups criteria in function of the stage of „scoring” and „weight” (Table 3).

Table 3. „Scoring” („a”) and „Weight” („p”) of resource criteria based on quantification of the weighted average

Region		Natural capital				Human capital			
		Total area	Agric. land	Relief	Forests	Populat. (no.inh.)	Life expect. (years)	Activity efficiency R.U.	Purches. power
	w	Weight (w) 1	Weight (w) 2	Weight (w) 1	Weight (w) 2	Weight (w) 1	Weight (w) 2	Weight (w) 3	Weight (w) 2
	a	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)	Points (a)
		$w_1 + w_2 + w_3 + w_4 = 1+2+1+2 = 6$				$w_1 + w_2 + w_3 + w_4 = 8$			
		Total area	% agro area out of total area	Presence NO Forms of relief					
Moldova Nord		3	3	4	3.75	6	3	3	2
Moldova Sud		2	3	5	3.25	5	2	2	3
Dunărea de Jos		2	4	4	1.67	2	2	3	4
Valahia Est		1	6	4	2.25	5	2	5	3
Valahia Vest		2	4	5	2.75	4	2	3	3
Oltenia		3	3	5	3.50	5	4	2	3
Banat		2	3	4	3.67	2	3	3	5
Crișana		1	4	4	2.67	2	1	2	6
Transilvania N		2	2	3	3.75	4	4	5	6
Transilvania S		1	2	3	4.33	1	5	3	6
Carpatica		3	2	3	4.25	3	5	3	5

Applying the weighted arithmetic mean formula, we may calculate, helped by the numbers from *SCORING* (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) and the fixed weight (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n), averages by main groups from criteria linked to life quality: natural capital, human capital (Table 4 and 5).

Table 4. Quantification of natural capital of the new regions

Region	Calculation of weighted arithmetic mean	M_p
Moldova Nord	$M_p = (3 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 + 3.75 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 20.50 / 6$	3.42
Moldova Sud	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 5 \times 1 + 3.25 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 19.50 / 6$	3.25
Dunărea de Jos	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 4 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 + 1.67 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 17.34 / 6$	2.89
Valahia Est	$M_p = (1 \times 1 + 6 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 + 2.25 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 21.50 / 6$	3.58
Valahia Vest	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 4 \times 2 + 5 \times 1 + 2.75 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 20.50 / 6$	3.42
Oltenia	$M_p = (3 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 5 \times 1 + 3.50 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 21.00 / 6$	3.50
Banat	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 + 3.67 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 19.34 / 6$	3.22
Crișana	$M_p = (1 \times 1 + 4 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 + 2.67 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 18.34 / 6$	3.06
Transilvania Nord	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 3 \times 1 + 3.75 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 16.50 / 6$	2.75
Transilvania Sud	$M_p = (1 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 3 \times 1 + 4.33 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 16.66 / 6$	2.78
Carpatica	$M_p = (3 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 3 \times 1 + 4.25 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 1 + 2 = 18.50 / 6$	3.08

Table 5. Quantification of human capital of the new regions

Region	Calculation of weighted arithmetic mean	M _p
Moldova Nord	$M_p = (6 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 2 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 25 / 8$	3.13
Moldova Sud	$M_p = (5 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 2 \times 3 + 3 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 21 / 8$	2.63
Dunărea de Jos	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 4 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 23 / 8$	2.88
Valahia Est	$M_p = (5 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 5 \times 3 + 3 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 30 / 8$	3.75
Valahia Vest	$M_p = (4 \times 1 + 2 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 3 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 23 / 8$	2.88
Oltenia	$M_p = (5 \times 1 + 4 \times 2 + 2 \times 3 + 3 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 25 / 8$	3.13
Banat	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 3 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 5 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 28 / 8$	3.50
Crișana	$M_p = (2 \times 1 + 1 \times 2 + 2 \times 3 + 6 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 22 / 8$	2.75
Transilvania Nord	$M_p = (4 \times 1 + 4 \times 2 + 5 \times 3 + 6 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 39 / 8$	4.88
Transilvania Sud	$M_p = (1 \times 1 + 5 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 6 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 32 / 8$	4.00
Carpatica	$M_p = (3 \times 1 + 5 \times 2 + 3 \times 3 + 5 \times 2) / 1 + 2 + 3 + 2 = 32 / 8$	4.00

Once quantified basic values concerning natural and human capital of the new regions, they may be processed on **bio harmonization principles** in the idea to evaluate the balance of resources between the new regions (Table 6 and 7).

Table 6. Index of bioharmonization integrative of the territorial unit from the proposed reorganization model

Region	Polyvalent potential of the new regions			Variation around the average deviation	
	Natural capital	Human capital	Polyvalent sum	Variation face to region average (6.59 p = 100%)	Variation face to deviation average (102 p.)
0	1	2	1+2	%	%
Moldova Nord	3.42	3.13	6.55	99.39	99.39 - 102 = - 2.61
Moldova Sud	3.25	2.63	5.88	89.23	89.23 - 102 = - 12.77
Dunărea de Jos	2.89	2.88	5.77	87.56	87.56 - 102 = - 14.44
Valahia Est	3.58	3.75	7.33	111.23	111.23 - 102 = + 9.23
Valahia Vest	3.42	2.88	6.30	95.60	95.60 - 102 = - 6.40
Oltenia	3.50	3.13	6.63	100.61	100.61 - 102 = - 1.39
Banat	3.22	3.50	6.72	101.97	101.97 - 102 = - 0.03
Crișana	3.06	2.75	5.81	88.16	88.16 - 102 = - 13.84
Transilvania Nord	2.75	4.88	7.63	115.78	115.78 - 102 = + 13.78
Transilvania Sud	2.78	4.00	6.78	102.88	102.88 - 102 = + 0.88
Carpatica	3.08	4.00	7.08	107.44	107.44 - 102 = + 5.44
Total polyvalent evaluation	x	x	72.48	x	x
Potential average per region	x	x	6.59	x	x
Extreme values	2.75 to 3.58	2.63 to 4.88	5.77 to 7.63	88.16 to 115.78	x
Deviation variation	-/+ 13 %	-/+ 30 %	x		-14 % ... + 14%

Table 7. Degree of territorial bioharmonization by polarization level of societal development

Territorial administrative organization	DIFFERENCE VARIATION			
	NATURAL CAPITAL	HUMAN CAPITAL	MODEL DIFFERENCE	REDUCTION OF POLARIZATION
CURRENT MODEL (40 counties)	x	x	-/+ 110 %	110 : 14 = 7.86
PROPOSED MODEL (12 regions)	-/+ 13 %	-/+ 30 %	-/+ 14 %	Conclusion: The territorial situation balances almost 8 times!

After definitization of preliminary studies, there will be made a SWOT Analyses, that has as an **OBJECTIVE:** to recommend the strategy that ensures the best alignment between the internal and external environment: to choose correct strategy, so that there may be adapted the strong points to opportunities, to minimize the risks and eliminate the weak points regarding the territorial administrative renewal of Romania.

Conclusions

(1) Romania's territorial reorganization is necessary („regionalization”) in order to solve current polarization between counties, in the present being registered a series of major imbalances: some of them being double as areas (8,700 km² face to 3,700 km²) and 3.5 times as population (772 thousands inhabitants face to 211 thousands), and as county GDP differences are over 5 times (50,000 thousand.lei face to 9,500 thousand), not to remind significant imbalances between counties and Bucharest zone (the average per county being 15 times smaller face to Bucharest!).

(2) The management of internal and European funds under legal and unequivocal conditions may be achieved by the proposed territorial-administrative reform, that foresees to organically create territorial units (that may have different names: departments, lands, regions etc.), more frequently being used „*administrative regions with a legal base of decentralization*”, respectively units with elected authorities and clear functions (managerial, economic, financial, cultural ones), these ones being as follows: Moldova Nord (MN/capital Iași), Moldova Sud (MS/capital Galați), Dunărea de Jos (DJ/capital Constanța), Valahia Est (VE/capital Ploiești), Valahia Vest (VV/capital Pitești), Oltenia (OT/capital Craiova), Banat (BT/capital Timișoara), Crișana (CS/capital Oradea), Transilvania Nord (TN/capital Cluj-Napoca), Transilvania Sud (TS/capital Sibiu), Carpatica (CP/capital Brașov) and Zona București (B).

(3) The territorial structures of the proposed model (named „regions”) are well balanced on harmonized polyvalent criteria, as follows:

- *as surface*: between approx.19,000 - 25,000 km² with an average of approx. 22,000 km²
- *as population*: between 1.1 - 2.3 thousand inhabitants per region, with an average of approx. 1.7 thousand inhabitants/region - *as density*: between 60 -90 inhabitants/km², with a national average of 82.50 inhabitants/km²
- *as regional GDP*: between 58 billion - 87 billion with an average of approx. 72 bill./region (except for Bucharest, with approx. 276 billion)

(4)The proposal regarding territorial reorganization, having at its basis a series of objective criteria and bio harmonization mechanisms (integration, improvement, balancing, equity of opportunities), makes a mitigation of imbalances between today's territorial structures, the proposed model reducing their number from 40 to 12, in addition also ensuring a **much better balance** between the new regional structures proposed by significant reduction of polarization of societal development and regarding life quality, reduction of almost 8 TIMES, i.e. from a difference of +/- 110 % to +/- 14 % (not taking into account Bucharest zone, that, as a metropolis, functions on different criteria, with a special development evolution).

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